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**MORPHOMETRIC ANALYSIS AND QUANTITATIVE COMPARISON OF
"SINUOUS RILLES" ON THE MOON AND ON VENUS**

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It is my duty to dedicate this space of my work to the people who have contributed to its realization, with their tireless support.

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Abstract

Earth's surface exhibits a great variety of geomorphologies, such as valleys, mountains, plains, streams and volcanoes, but to date, no extra large-scale lava channel, produced by effusive volcanism, such as sinuous rilles stretching over hundreds of kilometers, was detected. In fact, sinuous rilles have been observed only on some celestial bodies of our solar system including the Moon and Venus.

Sinuous rilles are considered to have formed as the result of thermomechanical erosion by large quantities of lava flowing on the surface of a planetary body. They have diverse morphologies, such as source depressions, tortuous paths or more linear ones narrowing and shallowing distally, and they can have depth and width ranges reaching hundreds of meters to kilometers, much greater in size compared to typical lava channels observed on terrestrial shield volcanoes.

In the past, with the advent of early space missions on the Moon, we began to observe various geomorphological features on the lunar surface, recognizing some large sinuous rilles and studying their distribution and origin. Later, an attempt was made to catalogue them utilizing improved remote sensing data sets, creating an atlas useful for easy localization and identification of specific morphological characteristics.

This study aims to update the existing global atlases of sinuous rilles of the Moon and Venus by integrating newly identified ones, in order to provide a detailed full assessment of global sinuous rille distributions and a morphometric analysis and quantitative comparison of these features between the two planetary bodies. The observations of planetary surfaces, through data provided by three spacecraft probes, the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter and Kaguya SELENE Orbiter for the Moon and Magellan for Venus, led to the detection of 264 lunar sinuous rilles (compared with previously known 194 sinuous rilles) and 372 sinuous rilles on Venus (compared with previously known 60 sinuous rilles), greatly improving the existing catalogs and their global distribution were revealed. Then, measurements of diverse parameters, such as length, distance, sinuosity index, width and depth were made, in order to identify potential morphological trends.

Results outlined that the geology and history of the two planetary bodies influenced the non-random distributions of sinuous rilles. In fact, their concentrations are greater in areas

affected by large volcanic effusions, i.e., maria regions for the lunar surface, while for Venus, the major concentration is near areas influenced by the interaction between mantle plumes and surface, i.e., coronae. Venusian sinuous rilles are characterized by greater lengths and distances than lunar ones, which, however, at the same distance, are longer and therefore more sinuous. Furthermore, with the same length, lunar sinuous rilles have greater widths than venusian ones, and their depth is greater for the same width. These properties indicate that a combination of mechanical and thermal erosion helped to build more meandering channels on the Moon, resulting in deeper and wider sections. Whereas on Venus, sinuous rilles are, shallower and longer channels, capable of reaching greater distances.

Introduction

The planetary surfaces in the solar system have different geomorphological features and some of the most widespread and pervasive are the river systems, in the broad sense, which include valleys and channels.

These river systems are particularly visible on some planetary bodies, such as the Moon, Mars, Venus, Io, Titan and the Earth, represented by channels, defined as the location where fluids flow, and by valleys, i.e., elongated depressions produced by the protracted action of fluid flow (Baker et al., 2015; Komatsu, 2007; Komatsu & Baker, 1996).

Through the observation of channels and valleys on the different planetary surfaces, we can devise classifications based on differences of their morphological characteristics. The variation of fundamental characteristics, such as length, width, sinuosity index, depth, inclination and fluid, determines distinctions in different landforms, such as valley networks on Mars originated by groundwater sapping or by surficial run-off, outflow channels produced by catastrophic flooding or by outpouring lava, gullies by surface run-off, Venusian canali produced by lava of silicate or exotic compositions causing mechanical erosion, and rilles resulted from thermomechanical erosion of lava.

The rilles can be divided into two subgroups: linear and sinuous rilles, based on the sinuosity index, determined by the formation process. Among the linear ones, some have a flat floor and relatively straight thalweg and sometimes they are associated with crater chains and arranged in echelon patterns, very similar to grabens, elongated blocks of crust that have collapsed between parallel faults, while others appear to be tension fractures in stress regions; the sinuous rilles are much more tortuous, due to the high sinuosity index and it is thought that they are similar to flow channels produced by lava flows on volcanoes of the Earth, but with a much greater order of magnitude in scale.

The word rille or rima to indicate these lunar landforms, derives from the Latin word "fissure" and it was first introduced by celestial observers, probably by the German astronomer Johann Schröter around 1800.

The first scientific study of lunar sinuous rilles was written at the end of the 1960s thanks to the Lunar Orbiter IV and V missions, which made some images of the lunar surface

with a resolution range between 58 and 134 m per pixel, covering 99% of the near side. Subsequently, with the SELENE mission launched in 2007, there was an improvement in the resolution of images up to 10 m per pixel with a global coverage, allowing an update by Hurwitz et al. (2013) of the catalog of lunar sinuous rilles produced originally by Peale et al., 1968, reaching a total of 194 sinuous rilles.

As for Venus, the Magellan mission launched in 1989 significantly improved the observations of the surface previously made by Arecibo Radio Telescope (Fig. 43). Head et al., 1991 observed some channels with a width range of about 1 km, departing from large pits, and continuing and narrowing for tens of kilometers downstream. These sinuous rilles show some morphological characteristics similar to those of terrestrial lava channels distributed on shield volcanoes and of lunar sinuous rilles. Baker et al. (1992, 1997) and Komatsu et al. (1993) mapped and investigated globally for more than 200 cases of Venusian channels and valleys, recognizing common morphological characteristics classified as 4 different types: simple, complex, compound and integrated (Fig. 1). Included in the simple ones there are Venusian sinuous rilles, which are recognized as similar to the lunar ones based on their morphological properties. Komatsu et al., (1993) identified 59 Venusian sinuous rilles.

Today, it is required to have a new catalog of sinuous rilles on Venus after approximately 30 years since the initial works by the Magellan scientists (Baker et al., 1992; Komatsu et al., 1993; Komatsu & Baker, 1992) in order to lay down the basis useful for future studies and use it as the starting point for identification of interesting locations from a scientific point of view. This work would be beneficial for upcoming new Venus missions such as VERITAS and EnVision. Furthermore, a new analysis of the lunar surface for updating the lunar sinuous rille catalog by Hurwitz et al. (2013), would be useful for a comparative study of sinuous rille morphologies of the two planetary bodies in order to understand the similarities and differences between them.

Lunar sinuous rilles

Sinuuous rilles have aroused a big interest since the Apollo expeditions and then they were studied more during the Lunar Orbiter IV and V missions. Starting from the data of these missions the first common characteristics of these channels emerged, such as the variable depth and width, the walls arranged parallel to each other that have lateral continuity and that in most cases the channels depart from associated depressions, flowing towards maria regions, without any kind of deposit left behind.

Past studies have mainly covered their origin, attributing it to two main hypotheses: an erosive action by a fluid or a flowing lava controlled by simple fracturing of basalt (Spudis et al., 1988). The scientific community, thanks to the improvement of data coming from the missions, discarded the hypothesis of the formation by intersection of different fractures (Oberbeck et al., 1969, 1971), especially for the origin of the sinuous type rilles, and then corroborated the idea of an erosive origin. Initially, erosion was thought to be caused by running water (Burke et al., 1970; Peale et al., 1968; Schubert et al., 1970), or ash flows (Cameron, 1964), or lava flows (Gornitz, 1973; Hulme, 1973) or by venting of gases along subsurface fractures (McCall, 1970; Schumm, 1970; Schumm et al., 1969), or directly formed by the collapse of lava tubes (Gornitz, 1973; Greeley, 1971) or more recently by the formation of surface lava channels (Carr, 1974; Hulme, 1973; Hurwitz et al., 2012; Williams et al., 2000).

Currently, the hypothesis of formation by erosion due to surface lava flow, seems to be the most accepted, but some doubts remain for the type of erosion capable of determining the peculiar morphology with levees built on the maria plains and with large channel lengths. The formation mechanisms hypothesized are mainly three: the first one regards the gradual cooling of lava, which allows the construction of a channel with levees above the mare region (Gregg & Greeley, 1993; Spudis et al., 1988); the second one considers the rilles as the result of mechanical erosion by lava inside the substrate (Siewert & Ferlito, 2008); the third one assume the thermal erosion as formation mechanism, due to thermal difference between lava and substrate (Carr, 1974; Coombs & Hawke, 1992; J. Head & Wilson, 1980; Hulme, 1973, 1982; Hurwitz et al., 2012; Kerr, 2009; Williams et al., 1998, 2000; Wilson & Head, 1981). In reality, it can be said that a combination of the

three mechanisms can be more plausible, as indicated by Hurwitz et al. (2012), because depending on the degree of consolidation and the inclination of substrate, either one process or the other may prevail. For example, if substrate is very solid and inclination is low, the construction of an overlapping riverbed with levees will prevail, and if inclination is high enough, the action of mechanical erosion will predominate, but if the substrate is poorly consolidated with a low inclination, thermal erosion will prevail, and if the inclination is high, the mechanical process will overcome. Moreover, in the case of a less consolidated substrate, the erosive process will be amplified.

The morphological characteristic that allows the distinction between sinuous rilles resulting from the different formation mechanisms is the trend of depth along the channel: if the depth decreases with increasing distance from the source, the prevailing mechanism is thermal erosion, while if the depth of the channel is irregular, the dominant process is mechanical erosion (Carr, 1974; Williams et al., 2000, 2001; Wilson & Head, 1981).

In particular, the construction and erosive processes, besides being very dependent on characteristics of the substrate, also depend on the type of lava flow and on duration of effusion: turbulent lava flows generate eroded channels in long intervals, such as months or years, while effusions of stationary or less turbulent lava type generate built channels, with raised levees, in weeks or months.

In 2020, a more specific study, concerning the morphology of sinuous rilles, related to the origin of the channel and the levees, updated the catalogue of the previous 194 rilles of Hurwitz et al. (2013) highlighting another 18 sinuous rilles only in a quadrant of the northern hemisphere of the lunar nearside, between 0° E to 90° E longitude and 0° N to 60° N latitude (Podda et al., 2020). This work outlined in the thesis instead, attempt to complete the work of Hurwitz et al. (2013) providing a more updated atlas of lunar sinuous rilles in a global view with additional morphometric measurements, so that formation processes can be fully understood.

Venusian sinuous rilles

Venus is the planet where many different types of channels were discovered after Moon and Mars, thanks to images produced by the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) of Magellan spacecraft (Fig. 3). It was not postulated that Venus was so populated by sinuous rilles. In fact, in 1992 after the first release of Magellan data, scientists identified about 200 relict channels and several valley landforms complexes (Baker et al., 1992, 1997; Komatsu et al., 1993).

Later, observing channels on Venusian surface, there was a first identification of the common features that allowed a classification of valley networks, distinguished in: simple, complex, compound and integrated channels (Baker et al., 1992, 1997; Komatsu et al., 1993) (Fig. 1).

Simple channels are characterized by a long and single main channel, distinguished in canali and sinuous rilles. Venusian sinuous rilles resemble a lot the lunar ones: departing from a depressed source area of almost circular shape and consisting of a single channel that narrows and shallows towards its terminus, characterized by width of about 1 - 2 km, lengths that ranges from tens to hundreds of km and they are usually associated with coronae areas or lowland regions.

Canali instead are generally longer and wider than sinuous rilles, departing from not distinguishable areas and terminate in vast areas of deposition characterized by dark colors on radar and they maintain a constant width (Baker et al., 1992, 1997; Gregg & Greeley, 1993; Komatsu et al., 1992; Komatsu & Baker, 1992). Although some canali may resemble sinuous rilles, there are general geomorphological properties distinguishing them, including the presence of a source depression and narrowing/shallowing trends of sinuous rilles.

Complex channels are characterized by anastomosed or braided patterns, so with many intertwined channels divided by several streamlined islands.

Compound channels consist in a combination of simple channel segments and complex channels, because they are generally located in mountainous regions and structurally deformed areas.

The integrated channels, that are very similar to valleys originated from groundwater sapping processes on Earth and Mars, are distinguished in rectangular, characterized by a geometric pattern stood out by right-angled bends of tributaries and unusually straight valley segments, due to structural deformations and sometimes associated with coronae; labyrinthic channels, the most widespread, are characterized by a pattern similar to the rectangular one but without the right-angled bends and with theater-headed tributaries. These are normally associated with structural deformation regions and also with corona areas (where mantle plumes are thought to interact with the surface) arranged concentrically around the corona, but often, they connect and originate the venusian sinuous rilles. Another type of integrated valley networks are the pitted or irregular ones located mainly in wrinkle ridged plains, and characterized by a series of coalesced pits or scalloped depressions with diameters up to several kilometers (Komatsu et al., 1993, 2001).

As already seen on the Moon, some valley networks may show meandering patterns, that normally on Earth, indicate a fluvial process, but in this case relate to lava flows. On Venus, the channels that expose this trend are the simple channels and in particular the canali characterized by features such as oxbows or meanders, which indicate lateral erosion of the channel, that migrate across the surface by cut and fill processes (Kargel et al., 1994; Komatsu et al., 1993).

A major difference between lunar and venusian channels is the course of longitudinal profiles of the surficial channels (e.g. Komatsu & Baker, 1994b). In fact, the venusian channels can move uphill on the topography due to a global deformation that occurred on Venus, probably due to tectonism and deformed the channels path.

To date, the only atlas of venusian sinuous rilles derive from the publication of Komatsu et al. (1993), that include a map, showing the global distribution of circa 60 known sinuous rilles, used to measure some morphometric parameters (e.g. Komatsu & Baker, 1994a; Oshigami et al., 2009), in order to have a comparison with terrestrial valley networks and to identify a fluid capable of the formation. This work aims to examine 372 venusian sinuous rilles in order to provide additional morphometric measurements to obtain a statistical comparison with lunar sinuous rilles.

Fig. 1 Channel's classification presented with examples from venusian surface. A and B are simple channels characterized by a single tortuous channel; B presents a theater-head source; C is a complex channel with an anastomosed pattern; D is a typical integrated channel presenting a rectangular pattern; E is a compound channel.

Methodology

Data

Data used in this thesis are exclusively rasters implemented in the QGIS software, in order to identify and map sinuous rilles on both Venus and Moon.

For the Moon portion of the project, the used base map was the mosaic from the Wide Angle Camera (WAC) of the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) (Speyerer et al., 2011) (Fig. 2), which includes more than 15,000 images, with global coverage, of the lunar surface. The mosaic was implemented with an equirectangular ocentric projection with central longitude at 0° and with a spatial resolution of 100 m/px. Furthermore, for a better observation, the images of the Terrain Camera (TC) from Kaguya SELENE orbiter (Fig. 2), with a spatial resolution of about 8 m/px, were used. Then, to better highlight the rilles, a selection of TC rasters with lighting from West (TC morning) and some with lighting from East (TC evening) were introduced.

Fig. 2 From left to right: Wide Angle Camera (WAC) on board of the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) and the Kaguya SELENE Orbiter with the Terrain Camera (TC) that produced the raster used in this study. (<https://www.lroc.asu.edu/about>, <https://global.jaxa.jp/projects/sas/selene/>)

Elevation is derived from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM), based on data from Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA) on board the LRO, with a spatial resolution of 118 m/px and global coverage (Smith et al., 2011). A better resolution was given by the merging of two DEMs, i.e. the one from LOLA and the other from Kaguya SELENE's TC data, obtaining a spatial resolution of 59 m/px and a coverage of 60° N and 60° S, therefore not optimal for polar areas (Barker et al., 2016). For this reason, in order to achieve greater details, the DEM from the data of TC on Kaguya SELENE (SLN TC DTM Map Seamless

V2.0) was inserted. This DEM consist of multiple square rasters with dimensions 3x3 degrees, covering globally, with a spatial resolution of ca. 8 m/px.

For the Venus portion of the project, the used base map was the mosaic produced by the Full resolution Basic Image Data Records (F-BIDRs) from the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) aboard Magellan spacecraft (Fig. 3, Fig. 2). This SAR is a "side-looking radar", capable of sending impulses at a certain angle in order to have a stereoscopic vision which, however, does not cover the entire surface. In fact, the Right Look images cover only 17% of the planet, while the Left Look images cover 98% of the surface, allowing an almost complete observation, with a spatial resolution of 75 m/px. The project, also for Venus, is based on an equirectangular ocentric projection with central longitude at 0°, in order to obtain measurements as real as possible.

Fig. 3 Left: Magellan spacecraft released by a Space Shuttle. Right: Surface coverage of the Full resolution Basic Image Data Records (F-BIDRs) from the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), only left look (top image) and stereoscopic look (bottom image).

<https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/missions/maellan/in-depth/> <https://astrogeology.usgs.gov/search/map/Venus/Magellan>

Elevation is obtained from the DEM produced by merging SAR stereoscopic data with Magellan's Altimeter and Radiometry Composite Data Record (ARCDR) data, resulting in a spatial resolution of 600 m / px and a vertical resolution of approximately 100 m, but with a global coverage of about 20% of the surface (Herrick et al., 2012) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Stereo - derived DTM areas of Venus' surface. (Herrick et al., 2012)

Measurements

First step was to identify the various sinuous rilles on the surface of both planetary bodies, starting from already existing atlases for the Moon and from the few publications on Venus. This study identified 264 sinuous rilles on the Moon and 372 on Venus, as well as 54 canali on venusian surface, for a total of 690 channels. The 54 canali have been identified, mainly because they present characteristics very similar to sinuous rilles and so they represent a possibility of comparison, to derive the discriminating elements between canali and sinuous rilles.

The next phase was mapping the sinuous rilles, creating a shapefile of linear features following the thalweg of sinuous rilles, in order to highlight the entire flow trend, from the possible source to its disappearance (Fig. 5). Tracing the thalweg, it was possible to measure the precise length of sinuous rilles and the distance from starting point to ending point, while for those departing from a source, the distance was measured from the source to the terminal part.

Fig. 5 Traced sinuous rilles on the Moon following the thalweg (Image centered long -45.62° lat 29.96°).

As a consequence, for each sinuous rilles, the sinuosity index was calculated through length and distance ratio, distinguishing them into different classes. The sinuous rilles with a sinuosity of less than 1.05 are characterized by an almost straight course, those with a sinuosity between 1.05 and 1.25 have a winding trend, those between 1.25 and 1.50 have a twisty channel and finally those with a sinuosity greater than 1.50 have a meandering trend (Fig. 6). Subsequently, in order to measure width and depth of sinuous rilles, it was necessary to produce sections perpendicular to the thalwegs, resulting in an average measurement for sinuous rilles without source and for canali on Venus, while just for sinuous rilles with a source, further perpendicular sections made possible to evaluate width and depth also at the beginning and end of flow.

$$\text{Sinuosity index} = \frac{\text{channel length}}{\text{downvalley distance}}$$

Sinuosity index	Channel trend
SI <1.05	Almost straight
1.05 ≤ SI <1.25	Winding
1.25 ≤ SI <1.50	Twisty
1.50 ≤ SI	Meandering

Fig. 6 Table with 4 classes of sinuosity index correlated with the respective channel trend. On top the formula to calculate sinuosity index.

Due to the high number of sinuous rilles for both the Moon (264) and Venus (426), it was appropriate to use different plugins, from QGIS repository, in order to simplify width and depth measurements: Profile Tool, to create sections perpendicular to channels and to acquire measurements (Fig. 7); Pick Layer, to adopt the appropriate DEM for each sinuous rilles, in order to have the right measurements.

All sinuous rilles have been assigned with geographical coordinates (GCS Moon and Venus 2015), in order to obtain an atlas for Venus and an updated one for the Moon, so that they can be identified and used in future studies.

Fig. 7 Section of a sinuous rille (Hadley rille) with measurements of width and depth (Image centered long 3.31° lat 25.96°).

Results

This study led to detection, mapping and measurement of 690 channels, 264 of which are lunar sinuous rilles, 372 are Venusian sinuous rilles and 54 are Venusian canali. On the lunar surface, compared to 194 sinuous rilles already detected (Hurwitz et al., 2013), 64 new sinuous rilles have been identified; while on the Venusian surface, in addition to the 60 sinuous rilles already identified (Komatsu et al., 1993), 312 new sinuous rilles and 54 canali were found.

The mapping shows a different distribution of the sinuous rilles on the various surfaces: on the Moon the greatest concentration, equal to 42%, occurs in the Oceanus Procellarum (Fig. 8), especially near the margins between mare and terrae, and then gradually decreases, moving on the terrae (Fig. 9).

Fig. 8 Distribution of sinuous rilles in the different regions of Moon's surface. The majority of sinuous rilles is located in the Procellarum region.

Fig. 9 Map illustrating identified sinuous rilles on the Moon. To note radial distribution of sinuous rilles around maria regions and the rare presence on them.

On Venus, the sinuous rilles distribution covers a larger area and is concentrated in the Scorisu Farra area with 45% of sinuous rilles (Fig. 10, Fig. 11).

Canali follows the same distribution as the venusian sinuous rilles and have an 11% concentration in the Henie quadrant (Fig. 12).

Fig. 10 Map illustrating identified venusian sinuous rilles (red) and the 54 canali (yellow) chosen for comparison.

Fig. 11 Distribution of sinuous rilles in the different regions on Venus's surface. The majority of sinuous rilles is located near Seoritsu Farra region.

Fig. 12 Distribution of canali in the different regions on Venus's surface. The majority of canali is located in the Henie quadrant.

Measurements are based on a variety of morphologic and morphometric characteristics, including variable length, width, depth, slope, and sinuosity index.

Length of each lunar sinuous rilles, calculated following the course of thalwegs, has an interval ranging from 1.6 km to 403.4 km on the Moon and the distance, calculated starting from the initial point or source to the end point with a straight segment, has an interval ranging from 910 m to 313.2 km. The greatest concentration is given by sinuous rilles with a length and distance in the order of tens of km (Fig. 13).

Venus presents sinuous rilles with a length in an interval between 3.4 km and 919.4 km and a distance in an interval between 1.6 km and 795.8. In this case, the concentration of sinuous rilles is greater for values up to 150 km (Fig. 14).

Venusian canali have a length between 12.1 km and 1993.1 km and a distance between 12.1 km and 1748.7 km. Exceptional case is represented by Baltis Vallis canale which reaches a length of 7052.4 km and a distance of 4482.3 km, distinguishing itself from the other channels in a clear way (Fig. 15).

Fig. 13 Plot illustrating the distribution of lunar sinuous rilles by length and distance.

Fig. 14 Plot illustrating the distribution of venusian sinuous rilles by length and distance.

Fig. 15 Plot illustrating the distribution of canali by length and distance.

The length's frequency graph shows that most of the lengths do not exceed 350 km for all sinuous rilles; moreover, the lunar ones do not exceed 403.4 km, while the venusian ones do not exceed 919.4 km, but the latter have a higher frequency in all classes and occupy classes of greater length than sinuous rilles on the Moon. Canali, on the other hand, have frequencies spread across all length categories, without showing specific trends (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16 Lengths' frequency of sinuous rilles and canali on the Moon and on Venus.

For distance, the majority of sinuous rilles does not go beyond 350 km, with lunar sinuous rilles not exceeding 313.2 km and venusian ones not exceeding 795.7 km. Also in this case, venusian sinuous rilles are more frequent in all classes and occupy classes of greater distance than lunar ones. Canali have very variable distances, without any concentration (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17 Distances' frequency of sinuous rilles and canali on the Moon and on Venus.

Sinuosity index is derived from the relationship between length and distance for all sinuous rilles and canali, then they are classified according to sinuosity classes. The most numerous class among all types of channels trends is the one between 1.05 and 1.25, therefore with a winding trend. For sinuosities greater than 1.50, with meandering trends, lunar sinuous rilles are more numerous than venusian ones, which are of the same amount of the almost straight trend sinuous rilles. Instead, canali are dominated by sinuosities between 1.05 and 1.25, resulting quite similar to sinuous rilles identified on Venus (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18 Frequency of sinuosity index of sinuous rilles and canali on the Moon and Venus.

On the Moon, sinuous rilles' index of sinuosity has a range from 1 to 2.64 and is plotted in a graph, compared with distance. On Venus, sinuosity index has a range from 1 to 2.80 (Fig. 20), quite similar to the lunar sinuous rilles (Fig. 19). Canali, instead, have sinuosity index from 1 to 1.75 (Fig. 21).

Fig. 19 Plot illustrating the distribution of lunar sinuous rilles by their distance and sinuosity index. The 4 colors indicate the different classes of sinuosity index on the plot: $SI < 1.05$ (blue), $1.05 \leq SI < 1.25$ (orange), $1.25 \leq SI < 1.50$ (grey), $1.50 \leq SI$ (yellow).

Fig. 20 Plot illustrating the distribution of venusian sinuous rilles by their distance and sinuosity index. The 4 colors indicate the different classes of sinuosity index on the plot: $SI < 1.05$ (blue), $1.05 \leq SI < 1.25$ (orange), $1.25 \leq SI < 1.50$ (grey), $1.50 \leq SI$ (yellow).

Fig. 21 Plot illustrating the distribution of canali by their distance and sinuosity index. The 4 colors indicate the different classes of sinuosity index on the plot: $SI < 1.05$ (blue), $1.05 \leq SI < 1.25$ (orange), $1.25 \leq SI < 1.50$ (grey), $1.50 \leq SI$ (yellow).

The width of sinuous rilles is measured from edge to edge of the two channel's sides, perpendicular to the thalweg. Lunar sinuous rilles have a channel width between 103.4 m

and 4192.6 m, but 88% of sinuous rilles has width between 100 m and 1500 m and they are more concentrated for small lengths (Fig. 22).

Fig. 22 Plot illustrating the distribution of lunar sinuous rilles by their length and average width.

On Venus, sinuous rilles have width in a range between 162.5 m and 5883.5 m, but 84% has width between 100 m and 1500 m and similarly to lunar sinuous rilles also the venusian ones have more short lengths, below 200 m (Fig. 23).

Fig. 23 Plot illustrating the distribution of venusian sinuous rilles by their length and average width.

As regards canali, the width ranges from 538.6 m to 12.8 km, but most of them have width that does not exceed 6 km and lengths that do not exceed 2000 km; Baltis Vallis with a length of 7052 km and Kinsei Valles with a width of 12.8 km are exceptions (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24 Plot illustrating the distribution of canali by their length and average width.

To better compare the width data of all channels, it is necessary to calculate the width to length ratio. Venusian sinuous rilles are concentrated for low ratios and therefore are characterized by longer lengths with a smaller channel width compared to lunar sinuous rilles, that have greater widths at the same length, covering a larger ratio range. Canali, generally, are characterized by low ratios and therefore will show morphologies with greater widths at the expense of lengths, obviously with the previous exceptions (Fig. 25).

Fig. 25 Frequency of the width/length ratio of sinuous rilles and canali on the Moon and on Venus.

Measurements of channel depth are performed by calculating the difference between the elevation of a thalweg point and the elevation of a point on the escarpment edge that divides the channel from the surrounding surface. This measurements are carried out as average measurements along the whole channel and only the sinuous rilles showing a source, have a measurement near the source and near the end of the channel (Fig. 7).

Furthermore, measurements are highly dependent on the coverage availability of a DTM, which, as already anticipated, for Venus is not global (Fig. 4). So, for the Moon, we have a global DTM, in fact, all 264 sinuous rilles are provided with at least one depth measurement; while on Venus, only 71 sinuous rilles and 16 canali are covered by the DTM, and therefore provided with at least one depth measurement.

On the Moon, sinuous rilles have an average depth between 2 m and 554 m, and 64% does not exceed 50 m of average depth with channel widths not exceeding 1 km. In a graph with average depth and average width, it is possible to notice that sinuous rilles with medium depths have a greater width, for example a sinuous rille with an average depth of 260 m does not have an average width less than 1450 m (Fig. 26).

Fig. 26 Plot illustrating the distribution of lunar sinuous rilles by their average depth and average width.

Venusian sinuous rilles have an average depth between 4 m and 418 m, but 77% has an average depth less than 50 m, therefore a greater amount than those on the Moon. In this case, no particular trend is observed, in the average depth graph with average width, in fact, width remains almost constant with increasing depth (Fig. 27). In a comparison

between sinuous rilles of the Moon and Venus, the latter are characterized by a lower average depth range than lunar ones for the same average widths (Fig. 28).

Fig. 27 Plot illustrating the distribution of venusian sinuous rilles by their average depth and average width.

Fig. 28 Plot illustrating the distribution of lunar and venusian sinuous rilles by their average depth and average width.

Canali show an average depth in an interval between 9 m and 104 m and the distribution is very random, probably also due to the lack of sufficient data, because there are only 16 canali with measured average depth (Fig. 29).

Fig. 29 Plot illustrating the distribution of canali by their average depth and average width.

For each sinuous rille the ratio between average width and average depth is calculated in order to highlight differences between data sets. In fact, it is possible to notice how lunar sinuous rilles have lower ratios than venusian ones, therefore they have channels with greater depths with the same width compared to those on Venus, which are less deep. Canali do not have distinctive characteristics as the dataset is too small (Fig. 30).

Fig. 30 Frequency of average width/average depth ratio for sinuous rilles and canali on the Moon and on Venus.

Among 690 channels, including lunar and venusian sinuous rilles and canali, identified on the different planetary surfaces, only 398 have a well-formed and identifiable source. They are unevenly distributed over the two planetary bodies. In fact, 262 sinuous rilles

with a source are observed on Venus, which are just over half of sinuous rilles present on the surface. While, on the Moon, sinuous rilles that present a source are fewer than average and compared to those on Venus: they are 119. Only 17 Venusian canali have a source, while the remaining 37 have none (Fig. 31).

Fig. 31 Plot illustrating the amount of sinuous rilles and canali identified with a source, on the Moon and on Venus.

Therefore, for all sinuous rilles of the Moon with a source, the depth at source and at end of the channel was measured, because they are covered by the global DTM, while on Venus only those with source and with coverage by the DTM are provided with two measures (Fig. 4). In fact, among 262 venusian sinuous rilles, only 36 fall within the area covered by the DTM, while among 17 channels, only 6 are within this area.

At the source, lunar sinuous rilles have depth between 8 m and 534 m, venusian ones between 4 m and 196 m, and canali between 10 m and 90 m. The graphs show the same trends valid for the average depth and average width: sinuous rilles on the Moon increase depth of the channel as width increases. Measurements of canali is not significant due to the small amount of data (Fig. 32).

Fig. 32 Plots illustrating the distribution of sinuous rilles and canali by the depth and width at their source.

The relationship between width and depth at the source, again shows the same trends that highlight how lunar sinuous rilles have channels with greater depths with the same width compared to venusian ones (Fig. 33).

Fig. 33 Frequency of the width/depth ratio at the source of sinuous rilles and canali, on the Moon and on Venus.

As regards the terminal part of channels, lunar sinuous rilles have depth between 2 m and 207 m, with the exception of Alpes Vallis with a depth of 1054 m, because it is located on the margin between a terra and a mare; while on Venus, sinuous rilles have a depth between 3 m and 126 m; canali have a depth at their terminus between 9 m and 119 m (Fig. 34). Also in this case, the comparison between different types of channels shows a non-variation in the trends, even for the ratio between width and depth (Fig. 35).

Fig. 34 Plots illustrating the distribution of sinuous rilles and canali by the depth and width at their terminal portion.

Fig. 35 Frequency of the width/depth ratio at the source of sinuous rilles and canali, on the Moon and on Venus.

Discussion

The distribution of sinuous rilles on the Moon is concentrated in a specific area: Oceanus Procellarum (Fig. 8). This is due to the presence of areas, which were affected by the outpouring of basaltic lavas which, flowing out, formed the rilles.

Observing the topography is possible to see that most of the sinuous rilles are not located on highlands and on maria, but they are radially arranged on the border between the highlands and the maria (Fig. 36). Highlands are the most ancient portion of the Moon's crust and it's characterized by an anorthosite composition, while maria are the product of extensive effusive volcanism processes, usually located in the lowlands, favoring the flow from higher surfaces towards less elevated ones with sinuous rilles. Furthermore, numerous sinuous rilles are located in the area that includes Oceanus Procellarum and Imbrium basin, that are part of the KREEP Terrane, composed of highly enriched magmas in incompatible and heat-producing elements preserved from the magma ocean period, that could have remained partially molten for several hundred million years. This remaining magma, tidally attracted by the Earth, is probably the origin of all the effusive volcanism, producing a high amount of sinuous rilles, localized in that specific region.

Fig. 36 Topography map of the Moon with the identified sinuous rilles. To note radial distribution of sinuous rilles around maria regions (lowlands) and the rare presence on them.

The distribution of venusian sinuous rilles is concentrated in Seoritsu Farra area and this is due to the presence of numerous coronae, probably formed by the manifestation of plumes, coming from mantle, to surface. In fact, sinuous rilles are located mainly near coronae, montes, tholi, fluctus, chasmata, paterae and in areas affected by deformation and volcanism (Fig. 11). A clear correlation between the sinuous rilles and the coronae is visible in Fig. 37 especially in the southern area, longitude 0° and latitude 75°S; for canali this correlation is much less evident.

Fig. 37 Map with the location of identified sinuous rilles (red), canali (yellow) and coronae (blue dot), in order to observe a distribution trend on Venus.

Canali are distributed in a similar way, but they are arranged in topographically less elevated areas than the sinuous rilles, which, as previously mentioned, are often associated with coronae and therefore in generally much higher areas (Fig. 38).

Fig. 38 Topography map of Venus with the identified sinuous rilles (white) and canali (purple). To note the higher elevation of sinuous rilles than canali that prefer low elevation regions.

Comparing measurements related to lengths and distances of sinuous rilles on the Moon and Venus, in a same graph (Fig. 39), it is possible to see that all the data fall below the length to distance ratio 1:1, because distance cannot be greater than length, for basic geometric reasons. It is also possible to observe how the concentration of lunar sinuous rilles is greater for shorter lengths and distances than sinuous rilles on Venus, as probably their formation took place in shorter times, limiting the distancing of flow from source. Their smaller extent may be due to limited effusive flow rate or even due to different ranges of temperatures of lava and the surrounding environment that affect the lava viscosity. Note that the lengths and distances range of lunar sinuous rilles is wider for lower values than the venusian one, because the dataset provides a higher resolution for the basemap used in sinuous rilles detection on the lunar surface, thanks to the implementation of rasters from Kaguya SELENE TC with a resolution of 8 m/px, compared to Magellan SAR images with a resolution of 75 m/px on Venus.

Moreover, two data series trends emerge from the comparative graph, in fact, the length over distance trend of the Moon is lower than the sinuous rilles trend of Venus: lunar rilles cover smaller distances, but have a greater length, while rilles on Venus cover longer distances, but have a shorter length, determined by more or less sinuous morphologies.

Fig. 39 Plot length vs. distance with sinuous rilles on the Moon and on Venus. To note the higher inclination of the venusian data trend than the lunar one. The grey line is the ratio 1:1 that is never overtaken by the data because distance cannot be greater than length.

Implementing results in a single graph with a relationship between length and distance, in logarithmic scale (Fig. 40), it is possible to notice how canali, which are morphologically similar to sinuous rilles, share an area with these, even if sinuous rilles are concentrated in portions with shorter lengths and distances, while canali are indeed longer and cover greater distances. Near the graph origin, there are some lunar sinuous rilles spaced from the high concentration of venusian sinuous rilles. The detection of these sinuous rilles is the consequence of higher spatial resolution on the Moon, which allows sinuous rilles on the surface to be identified in more detail. On Venus, on the other hand, the resolution does not allow to identify sinuous rilles smaller than the available spatial resolution, but this does not exclude that they are really present on the surface.

Fig. 40 Logarithmic plot length vs. distance with sinuous rilles and canali on the Moon and on Venus. To note the different portions occupied by the 3 series of data. The moon series is closer to the origin probably for the higher spatial resolution of rasters.

On the Moon, observing the sinuosity index compared to distance (Fig. 19, Fig. 41), it is possible to note that sinuous rilles with short distances have a greater sinuosity than those with large distances and this is probably determined by the time taken by the flux to flow with a tortuous trend, which makes it difficult to reach large distances in a rapid way, maintaining a low viscosity.

A similar case occurs for sinuous rilles on Venus, which with greater distances have a lower sinuosity index, even if the phenomenon is more dilated towards greater distances,

because on the Moon, sinuous rilles can have a sinuosity of 1.60 at distances of about 200 km, while the same sinuosity on Venus is also present at distances of about 500 km (Fig. 20, Fig. 41). Probably, this is again a symptom of a limited flow rate of the effusive flux on the Moon compared to flow rates on Venus or even due to different temperatures of lava and the surrounding environment in the two planetary bodies, which determine different viscosities.

Fig. 41 Plot sinuosity index vs. distance with sinuous rilles on the Moon and on Venus.

Venusian sinuous rilles have a sinuosity index between 1 and 2.80, while canali between 1 and 1.77, determining another essential characteristic for their distinction. In fact, the sinuous rilles are actually more sinuous and cover less distance than canali: the graph (Fig. 42) shows that only 6 canali are included in the portion where sinuosity index is greater than 1.50, compared to the 41 venusian sinuous rilles.

Fig. 42 Plot sinuosity index vs. distance with sinuous rilles and canali on Venus.

The results, obtained from the measurements of channel's width, show that venusian sinuous rilles have low width to length ratios. In fact, they have longer lengths with smaller channel width compared to lunar sinuous rilles, that have larger ratios, and so they are characterized by greater widths at the same length (Fig. 22, Fig. 23).

Comparing average depths of sinuous rilles, it is possible to observe that the venusian ones are characterized by lower average depths than lunar ones. The same trend is observed for the source portion and terminal portion of sinuous rilles: lunar sinuous rilles have greater depths than venusian ones with the same width (Fig. 30).

Conclusion

Discussion outlined that the distribution of sinuous rilles on the two planetary surfaces is not accidental. Lunar sinuous rilles are concentrated on the margins between terrae and maria, due to the proximity of areas characterized by effusive volcanism such as the KREEP Terrane. The lack of sinuous rilles inside the maria is probably due to the overlay of channel structures by huge effusive flows, which have canceled or concealed the morphologies. Instead, venusian sinuous rilles are located on the entire planetary surface, just to concentrate in areas affected by probable interaction with Venus's mantle, forming the coronae. On the remaining surface portions, they are however located, albeit in smaller numbers, around montes, tholi, fluctus, chasmata, paterae and in areas affected by deformation and volcanism. Canali, on Venus, are arranged over the entire surface, with a greater presence in the low elevation areas and especially in the Henie quadrant.

Venusian sinuous rilles have greater length and distance than lunar sinuous rilles, however by comparing distance with length, it is possible to notice that at the same distance lunar sinuous rilles are longer than venusian ones. This will translate into greater sinuosity of lunar sinuous rilles compared to those on Venus. In general, canali are much longer than sinuous rilles and also have lower sinuosity indices, in fact, they show almost straight morphologies of the channel.

Lunar sinuous rilles are more sinuous than Venus, as 57 lunar sinuous rilles have sinuous index greater than 1.50, with a meandering morphology, opposed to venusian ones which have sinuosity index lower than 1.05 and with same amount greater than 1.50. Canali have low sinuosity compared to venusian sinuous rilles, a distinctive element useful for remote sensing.

Talking about channels' width, lunar sinuous rilles have a greater width than the venusian sinuous rilles with equal length, which instead, have a smaller width for greater lengths. Canali's width is almost constant along the course of the channel, that favors long lengths.

Depth measurements show that lunar sinuous rilles have greater average depths than venusian sinuous rilles with the same average width. The same trend is observed at the source and at the terminus of channels, maintaining a constant ratio between width and

depth. Basically, increasing width increases depth of the channel. Canali, due to the small number of data, do not show any particular trend.

Lunar sinuous rilles, which are longer but cover less distances, because morphologically more sinuous, did not move far from the source, either due to a limited flow rate of lava flow or due to shorter formation times. Therefore, the combination of mechanical and thermal erosion acted more in the construction of more meandering channels, rather than making them reach long distances, as demonstrated by greater depths and widths of the channel sections. On Venus, sinuous rilles are characterized by longer and less sinuous channels, reaching great distances. This probably occurred due to the enormous flow rates of lava flows and due to high temperatures of fluid and the environment, which decreased the viscosity of the lava, favoring its flow, which inhibited the formation of channels with great depths and widths. For canali, it is important to know the discriminating morphologies from venusian sinuous rilles, in order to obtain an effective identification. In fact, canali are certainly longer than sinuous rilles, they generally have an almost constant width and depth along the entire path and they have a slightly lower sinuosity, allowing greater distances to be reached.

The Moon already had numerous missions, which documented the entire surface, resulting in huge datasets, that allowed the expansion of the atlas of lunar sinuous rilles; instead, for Venus, currently the best dataset available for observation of channels is the one from Magellan, which however is not sufficient for the complete identification of channels and mainly all the sinuous rilles (Fig. 43).

COMPARISON OF MAGELLAN AND PAST VENUS MISSIONS

Fig. 43 Plot illustrating spatial resolution and coverage of all the data available from Venus' missions compared with scale of different morphologies. To note how Magellan data covers quite all the planetary surface, but its spatial resolution is just enough to observe channels and it's very poor for sinuous rilles detection.

For this reason, this atlas of venusian sinuous rilles tries to be a support and a guide for future missions, in order to have characteristic and unique elements to perform an effective detection of canali and sinuous rilles. Next missions such as VERITAS and EnVision, respectively with VISAR (Venus Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar) and VenSAR (Venus Synthetic Aperture Radar), will allow to increase spatial resolution of the Venus surface datasets, favoring a better identification of sinuous rilles and therefore a fulfilment of this atlas. Finally, with this atlas there is the hope to spur scientific research towards more studies, about the almost unknown planet Venus, compared to other planets, that are not similar to our own.

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Appendix

Atlas of lunar sinuous rilles

ID	Name	Location	Length (km)	Distance (km)	Sinuosity (adim)	Width Source (m)	Width End (m)	Width Avarage (m)	Depth Source (m)	Depth End (m)	Depth Avarage (m)	Source?	Width/Lenght (adim)	Width/Depth Source (adim)	Width/Depth End (adim)	Width/Depth Avarage (adim)	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)
1		Mare Smythii	25,211	21,416	1,177	1111,168	1482,584	1296,876	98	22	60	YES	19,440	11,338	67,390	21,615	1,359	83,163
2		Mare Smythii	24,228	21,018	1,153	549,216	340,08	444,648	18	5	11,5	YES	54,488	30,512	68,016	38,665	0,806	83,518
3		Mare Smythii	42,351	40,171	1,054	429,471	533,698	481,585	20	23	21,5	YES	87,941	21,474	23,204	22,399	0,142	81,698
4		Mare Smythii	38,576	36,057	1,07			585,899			15	NO	65,841			39,060	0,635	82,043
5		Mare Smythii	43,433	38,889	1,117			1097,164			48	NO	39,587			22,858	0,171	81,542
6		Mare Smythii	31,064	30,592	1,015			827,264			21	NO	37,550			39,394	-0,733	82,227
7		Nectaris	15,632	13,884	1,126	1030,614	1085,105	1057,86	107	126	61	YES	14,777	9,632	8,612	17,342	-12,612	38,608
8		Fecunditas	28,587	28,118	1,017			1036,31			172	NO	27,585			6,025	-2,753	42,074
9		Fecunditas	43,855	35,531	1,234	1874,512	628,761	1251,637	197	40	118,5	YES	35,038	9,515	15,719	10,562	-3,11	42,264
10		Fecunditas	3,407	3,403	1,001	585,03	383,124	484,077	31	13	22	YES	7,038	18,872	29,471	22,004	-2,91	42,329
11		Fecunditas	49,867	48,646	1,025			797,707			39	NO	62,513			20,454	-2,739	42,178
12		Fecunditas	26,69	23,693	1,126			866,765			35	NO	30,793			24,765	-2,663	41,537
13		Fecunditas	28,03	24,638	1,138			861,359			62	NO	32,542			13,893	-1,78	43,189
14		Tranquillitatis	171,218	144,85	1,182			848,208			20	NO	201,859			42,410	-0,401	28,66
15		Tranquillitatis	43,751	42,929	1,019			286,257			19	NO	152,838			15,066	3,04	27,381
16		Tranquillitatis	6,687	6,196	1,079			169,579			2	NO	39,433			84,790	2,947	27,475
17		Tranquillitatis	19,832	18,094	1,096			889,22			58	NO	22,303			15,331	-0,408	28,672
18		Tranquillitatis	3,696	3,504	1,055			410,505			23	NO	9,004			17,848	-0,779	28,879
19		Tranquillitatis	10,869	8,772	1,239			956,714			37	NO	11,361			25,857	-0,4	28,687
20		Tranquillitatis	15,071	13,015	1,158	985,558	206,407	595,983	77	14	45,5	YES	25,288	12,799	14,743	13,099	-0,564	28,2
21		Sinus Aestuum	38,821	35,334	1,099			1009,463			109	NO	38,457			9,261	9,302	11,013
22		Sinus Aestuum	13,695	13,569	1,009			914,421			167	NO	14,977			5,476	9,494	11,647
23		Sinus Aestuum	13,318	12,748	1,045			282,723			24	NO	47,106			11,780	10,227	10,931
24		Sinus Aestuum	4,475	2,938	1,523			174,078			12	NO	25,707			14,507	10,157	11,166
25		Sinus Aestuum	38,503	26,515	1,452			609,982			36	NO	63,122			16,944	9,314	12,121

26		Tranquillitatis	23,449	17,883	1,311	1069,609	175,912	622,761	110	4	57	YES	37,653	9,724	43,978	10,926	12,298	26,258
27	Rima Jansen	Serenitatis	49,538	41,679	1,189	2900,044	722,601	1811,323	181	60	120,5	YES	27,349	16,022	12,043	15,032	13,827	29,83
28		Serenitatis	12,823	12,747	1,006			889,507			87	NO	14,416			10,224	14,594	27,359
29		Serenitatis	38,519	37,973	1,014			575,374			24	NO	66,946			23,974	15,045	27,342
30		Serenitatis	20,452	17,343	1,179	809	628,355	718,678	11	20	15,5	YES	28,458	73,545	31,418	46,366	14,825	26,925
31		Serenitatis	10,84	7,36	1,473	1020,675	446,021	733,348	15	16	15,5	YES	14,782	68,045	27,876	47,313	13,961	28,295
32		Serenitatis	5,552	5,013	1,108			335,955			8	NO	16,526			41,994	19,573	27,212
33	Rima Reiko/Rima Marcello	Serenitatis	48,001	39,016	1,23			585,052			21	NO	82,046			27,860	19,231	27,435
34		Serenitatis	2,858	1,609	1,776	603,786	288,05	445,918	28	6	17	YES	6,409	21,564	48,008	26,230	18,951	27,486
35		Serenitatis	2,766	2,583	1,071	617,053	272,914	444,984	24	10	17	YES	6,216	25,711	27,291	26,176	17,348	29,545
36		Serenitatis	11,296	11,137	1,014			746,189			33	NO	15,138			22,612	17,896	28,988
37		Serenitatis	40,221	38,19	1,053			744,785			24	NO	54,004			31,033	17,916	28,689
38	Rima Carmen	Serenitatis	27,781	22,496	1,235			1291,402			109	NO	21,512			11,848	19,676	29,342
39		Serenitatis	20,587	15,833	1,3			500,676			15	NO	41,118			33,378	23,142	28,57
40	Rimae Posidonius	Serenitatis	202,521	77,922	2,599			1204,486			101	NO	168,139			11,926	31,851	28,023
41		Serenitatis	20,696	18,873	1,097			703,34			66	NO	29,425			10,657	28,511	28,263
42		Serenitatis	5,487	5,343	1,027			646,151			83	NO	8,492			7,785	28,307	28,314
43		Serenitatis	6,974	6,875	1,014	756,48	675,473	715,977	69	53	61	YES	9,741	10,963	12,745	11,737	28,21	28,375
44		Serenitatis	11,363	7,904	1,438			441,777			44	NO	25,721			10,040	28,407	26,46
45		Serenitatis	16,082	11,814	1,361			329,584			8	NO	48,795			41,198	41,606	23,185
46		Serenitatis	28,595	21	1,362	1981,672	595,014	1288,343	250	20	135	YES	22,195	7,927	29,751	9,543	41,365	21,406
47	Vallis Alpes	Imbrium	204,803	186,948	1,096	1038,994	5302,435	3170,715	52	1057	554,5	YES	64,592	19,981	5,016	5,718	49,886	5,537
48		Imbrium	176,871	99,092	1,785	1959,444	1475,297	1717,371	148	65	106,5	YES	102,989	13,239	22,697	16,126	48,771	-0,422
49		Imbrium	14,963	10,695	1,399	1153,974	1465,055	1309,515	75	89	82	YES	11,426	15,386	16,461	15,970	50,084	-1,469
50		Imbrium	116,587	88,871	1,312	1105,618	493,092	799,355	41	17	29	YES	145,851	26,966	29,005	27,564	48,989	-3,76
51		Imbrium	28,564	21,821	1,309	694,485	786,123	740,304	46	18	32	YES	38,584	15,098	43,674	23,135	47,135	-4,243
52		Imbrium	10,209	8,904	1,147			542,274			9	NO	18,826			60,253	46,923	-4,383

53		Imbrium	12,853	10,036	1,281			1744,453			128	NO	7,368			13,629	48,843	-0,331
54	Rima Hadley	Imbrium	171,267	94,723	1,808	2202,111	2586,779	2394,445	372	135	253,5	YES	71,527	5,920	19,161	9,446	24,403	2,746
55	Rima Conon	Imbrium	38,946	34,268	1,137			1248,901			104	NO	31,184			12,009	18,259	2,272
56		Imbrium	8,629	8,529	1,012	1307,239	1064,259	1185,749	54	73	63,5	YES	7,277	24,208	14,579	18,673	18,259	1,83
57		Imbrium	4,678	4,43	1,056			1567,518			71	NO	2,984			22,078	18,216	1,759
58		Imbrium	22,043	16,058	1,373			742,872			16	NO	29,673			46,430	18,334	1,426
59		Imbrium	6,663	6,491	1,026			647,126			21	NO	10,296			30,816	18,915	1,423
60		Sinus Aestuum	59,509	46,026	1,293			792,926			51	NO	75,050			15,548	5,073	1,546
61		Sinus Aestuum	19,361	14,463	1,339			566,222			71	NO	34,193			7,975	6,265	1,89
62		Humboldt	49,469	34,58	1,431	1445,045	2106,291	1775,668	103	107	105	YES	27,859	14,030	19,685	16,911	-48,176	87,819
63		Schrödinger	321,179	313,211	1,025			3488,271			131	NO	92,074			26,628	-76,765	132,78
64		Schrödinger	80,658	59,524	1,355			4192,623			49	NO	19,238			85,564	-74,737	140,143
65		Thomson	53,294	33,462	1,593	1689,127	1500,91	1595,019	245	62	153,5	YES	33,413	6,894	24,208	10,391	-33,416	143,477
66		Jules Verne	8,802	7,284	1,208			410,187			27	NO	21,459			15,192	-34,717	145,386
67		Thomson	24,063	20,279	1,187			1323,262			15	NO	18,185			88,217	-31,228	161,715
68		Thomson	74,815	51,137	1,463	1593,411	529,21	1061,311	135	33	84	YES	70,493	11,803	16,037	12,635	-30,231	161,174
69		Thomson	56,706	50,839	1,115			2780,231			327	NO	20,396			8,502	-26,835	164,467
70		Orientale	83,617	52,012	1,608			954,371			163	NO	87,615			5,855	-25,847	-95,048
71		Orientale	25,554	16,024	1,595			1106,708			155	NO	23,090			7,140	-22,048	-82,983
72		Orientale	17,515	15,476	1,132	676,96	338,496	507,728	54	18	36	YES	34,497	12,536	18,805	14,104	-22,206	-86,687
73		Orientale	15,999	8,287	1,931			423,136			25	NO	37,811			16,925	-21,818	-85,712
74		Orientale	29,736	22,798	1,304			497,927			33	NO	59,720			15,089	-19,364	-85,001
75		Orientale	69,971	36,309	1,927			694,969			80	NO	100,682			8,687	-13,67	-85,913
76		Orientale	29,356	23,284	1,261	318,022	175,401	246,712	14	7	10,5	YES	118,989	22,716	25,057	23,496	-12,589	-87,436
77		Orientale	113,615	84,931	1,338			385,073			25	NO	295,048			15,403	-11,353	-88,774
78		Orientale	35,778	26,746	1,338	835,833	2126,021	1480,927	181	34	107,5	YES	24,159	4,618	62,530	13,776	-11,855	-80,877
79		Orientale	7,566	4,763	1,588	628,806	620,062	624,434	66	55	60,5	YES	12,117	9,527	11,274	10,321	-10,417	-83,136
80		Orientale	40,311	29,445	1,369	395,443	329,27	362,357	46	11	28,5	YES	111,247	8,597	29,934	12,714	-10,033	-83,37

81		Orientele	62,406	40,448	1,543	915,55	506,6	711,075	98	35	66,5	YES	87,763	9,342	14,474	10,693	-8,251	-96,533
82		Orientele	6,981	6,846	1,02			674,816			29	NO	10,345			23,270	-8,471	-96,511
83		Nubium	49,851	42,64	1,169	1580,904	1132,001	1356,452	86	78	82	YES	36,751	18,383	14,513	16,542	-32,607	-16,495
84		Nubium	20,029	16,819	1,191			1051,866			18	NO	19,041			58,437	-33,578	-16,603
85		Nubium	56,98	39,304	1,45	3110,485	1360,975	2235,73	209	54	131,5	YES	25,486	14,883	25,203	17,002	-29,968	-24,606
86		Procellarum	17,16	15,332	1,119			396,782			28	NO	43,248			14,171	-6,068	-50,301
87		Procellarum	28,075	25,972	1,081			1745,107			159	NO	16,088			10,976	6,963	-66,829
88		Procellarum	26,047	18,102	1,439	1756,927	934,552	1345,74	164	79	121,5	YES	19,355	10,713	11,830	11,076	20,354	-74,506
89		Nubium	18,544	10,282	1,804	334,019	212,791	273,405	11	4	7,5	YES	67,826	30,365	53,198	36,454	-18,683	-23,122
90		Nubium	9,086	6,627	1,371	334,019	278,529	306,274	11	8	9,5	YES	29,666	30,365	34,816	32,239	-18,683	-23,122
91		Nubium	67,166	41,692	1,611			563,915			15	NO	119,107			37,594	-18,48	-24,77
92		Procellarum	82,43	62,841	1,312			293,825			9	NO	280,541			32,647	-16,221	-33,588
93		Procellarum	71,097	51,656	1,376			450,691			22	NO	157,751			20,486	-16,046	-27,389
94		Procellarum	22,044	14,601	1,51			331,325			17	NO	66,533			19,490	-18,307	-26,328
95		Procellarum	84,291	54,837	1,537	516,28	266,824	391,552	20	17	18,5	YES	215,274	25,814	15,696	21,165	-15,281	-26,216
96		Procellarum	16,643	12,923	1,288			320,24			16	NO	51,970			20,015	-16,029	-25,204
97		Procellarum	90,203	73,629	1,225	751,41	345,948	548,679	18	11	14,5	YES	164,400	41,745	31,450	37,840	-15,03	-35,875
98		Procellarum	84,822	68,286	1,242			370,732			17	NO	228,796			21,808	-15,52	-35,602
99	Rimae Herigonius	Procellarum	43,442	29,873	1,454	558,529	581,353	569,941	62	12	37	YES	76,222	9,009	48,446	15,404	-12,483	-37,371
100	Rimae Herigonius	Procellarum	300,363	186,645	1,609	626,567	337,756	482,162	44	6	25	YES	622,950	14,240	56,293	19,286	-11,838	-35,867
101	Rimae Herigonius	Procellarum	13,216	8,362	1,58			634,655			25	NO	20,824			25,386	-11,705	-35,378
102		Procellarum	7,153	3,923	1,823			323,765			25	NO	22,093			12,951	-6,355	-26,539
103		Procellarum	16,698	12,145	1,375			485,287			9	NO	34,409			53,921	-1,662	-25,891
104		Procellarum	33,472	32,702	1,024			448,782			26	NO	74,584			17,261	-3,053	-26,599
105		Procellarum	48,994	40,994	1,195	681,958	742,948	712,453	18	16	17	YES	68,768	37,887	46,434	41,909	-1,056	-25,344
106		Procellarum	10,421	9,52	1,095			508,696			30	NO	20,486			16,957	1,083	-37,11
107		Procellarum	65,007	54,663	1,189			430,732			14	NO	150,922			30,767	3,805	-42,62
108		Procellarum	18,58	15,043	1,235			238,222			14	NO	77,994			17,016	4,686	-46,346

109		Procellarum	15,636	12,21	1,281			221,494			9	NO	70,593			24,610	4	-46,665
110		Procellarum	6,672	6,195	1,077			220,432			8	NO	30,268			27,554	3,722	-46,729
111		Procellarum	24,657	21,053	1,171			385,195			11	NO	64,012			35,018	6,582	-51,98
112		Procellarum	30,85	18,033	1,711			946,024			66	NO	32,610			14,334	7,72	-50,715
113		Procellarum	22,385	14,924	1,5	628,302	403,368	515,835	18	18	18	YES	43,396	34,906	22,409	28,658	8,028	-53,797
114		Procellarum	17,752	11,944	1,486	734,486	491,189	612,838	29	24	26,5	YES	28,967	25,327	20,466	23,126	8,028	-53,797
115	Rima Seuss	Procellarum	285,008	203,759	1,399	932,21	414,521	673,366	59	11	35	YES	423,259	15,800	37,684	19,239	8,58	-48,602
116		Procellarum	76,282	31,523	2,42	548,032	285,826	416,929	41	5	23	YES	182,962	13,367	57,165	18,127	9,311	-48,508
117		Procellarum	23,096	19,118	1,208			376,664			17	NO	61,317			22,157	8,448	-48,201
118		Procellarum	14,659	11,973	1,224	2192,044	1597,3	1894,672	462	42	252	YES	7,737	4,745	38,031	7,519	11,275	-50,465
119		Procellarum	56,732	44,311	1,28			593,468			13	NO	95,594			45,651	13,67	-48,027
120		Procellarum	4,847	4,215	1,15			370,036			7	NO	13,099			52,862	12,052	-49,737
121		Procellarum	4,214	1,909	2,207	373,638	351,888	362,763	28	40	34	YES	11,616	13,344	8,797	10,670	12,463	-50,189
122		Procellarum	15,986	12,601	1,269	472,308	263,602	367,955	12	5	8,5	YES	43,446	39,359	52,720	43,289	12,348	-50,175
123		Procellarum	19,734	16,843	1,172			535,399			28	NO	36,858			19,121	11,968	-53,544
124		Procellarum	14,92	10,319	1,446			552,19			8	NO	27,020			69,024	11,604	-54,002
125	Rima Galilei	Procellarum	201,671	149,522	1,349			298,544			13	NO	675,515			22,965	11,036	-57,619
126		Procellarum	12,31	10,222	1,204			330,734			29	NO	37,220			11,405	11	-57,48
127		Procellarum	7,354	7,131	1,031			694,417			52	NO	10,590			13,354	10,97	-57,058
128		Procellarum	60,013	37,692	1,592	592,67	773,933	683,302	18	34	26	YES	87,828	32,926	22,763	26,281	9,116	-57,335
129		Procellarum	18,312	14,386	1,273	1161,939	452,125	807,032	162	27	94,5	YES	22,691	7,172	16,745	8,540	13,945	-49,397
130		Procellarum	5,391	4,407	1,223	582,698	234,609	408,654	56	6	31	YES	13,192	10,405	39,102	13,182	14,404	-50,122
131	Rima Marius	Procellarum	310,875	167,53	1,856	1326,709	304,693	815,701	245	9	127	YES	381,114	5,415	33,855	6,423	14,506	-48,55
132		Procellarum	79,507	51,287	1,55	2954,029	279,818	1616,923	199	13	106	YES	49,172	14,844	21,524	15,254	14,819	-51,043
133		Procellarum	7,28	6,108	1,192			332,914			12	NO	21,868			27,743	13,241	-56,999
134		Procellarum	12,702	11,993	1,059			340,573			33	NO	37,296			10,320	12,913	-56,678
135		Procellarum	56,646	48,825	1,16	1332,156	769,562	1050,859	218	72	145	YES	53,904	6,111	10,688	7,247	13,666	-55,878
136		Procellarum	41,623	32,944	1,263	651,772	300,016	475,894	68	10	39	YES	87,463	9,585	30,002	12,202	14,217	-55,955

137		Procellarum	7,491	6,828	1,097			237,375			7	NO	31,558			33,911	14,444	-56,792
138		Procellarum	42,766	25,089	1,705	631,527	442,2	536,864	53	14	33,5	YES	79,659	11,916	31,586	16,026	12,799	-57,788
139		Procellarum	16,912	13,823	1,223	456,279	292,271	374,275	25	9	17	YES	45,186	18,251	32,475	22,016	13,435	-58,983
140		Procellarum	3,566	3,515	1,015			546,98			85	NO	6,519			6,435	13,686	-57,965
141		Procellarum	240,818	168,153	1,432	587,077	381,233	484,155	12	10	11	YES	497,399	48,923	38,123	44,014	18,542	-47,168
142		Procellarum	54,343	40,659	1,337			315,75			12	NO	172,108			26,313	20,239	-49,342
143		Procellarum	48,189	34,546	1,395	609,402	480,258	544,83	17	23	20	YES	88,448	35,847	20,881	27,242	22,409	-44,934
144	Rima Brayley	Imbrium	403,41	288,091	1,4			390,178			21	NO	1.033,913			18,580	21,144	-40,165
145		Imbrium	54,36	51,154	1,063			645,384			29	NO	84,229			22,255	20,695	-35,783
146		Imbrium	9,624	8,077	1,192			434,633			26	NO	22,143			16,717	21,6	-35,235
147	Rima Wan-Yu	Imbrium	15,896	13,261	1,199			1209,509			55	NO	13,143			21,991	20,168	-31,392
148		Imbrium	12,224	10,208	1,197			1531,27			24	NO	7,983			63,803	20,88	-30,611
149	Rima Euler	Imbrium	191,844	141,158	1,359			308,357			15	NO	622,149			20,557	22,413	-27,474
150		Imbrium	15,712	13,491	1,165	467,247	331,281	399,264	8	14	11	YES	39,352	58,406	23,663	36,297	23,352	-34,811
151		Imbrium	22,894	20,182	1,134	428,09	306,473	367,282	8	2	5	YES	62,334	53,511	153,237	73,456	24,231	-30,569
152		Imbrium	18,415	17,047	1,08			334,934			5	NO	54,981			66,987	24,083	-31,052
153		Imbrium	11,251	10,853	1,037			369,274			5	NO	30,468			73,855	23,999	-30,932
154		Imbrium	38,374	35,573	1,079			275,781			18	NO	139,147			15,321	24,699	-31,328
155		Imbrium	36,964	33,976	1,088			296,659			10	NO	124,601			29,666	22,351	-30,187
156		Imbrium	60,798	50,209	1,211	796,995	812,12	804,558	24	35	29,5	YES	75,567	33,208	23,203	27,273	19,089	-23,312
157	Rima Draper	Imbrium	187,346	119,358	1,57	662,41	567,135	614,773	55	27	41	YES	304,740	12,044	21,005	14,994	18,403	-28,025
158	Rima Diophantus	Imbrium	236,849	138,059	1,716	658,805	595,402	627,103	46	26	36	YES	377,688	14,322	22,900	17,420	28,446	-35,71
159	Rima Delisle	Imbrium	76,994	60,523	1,272	1134,09	555,15	844,62	191	12	101,5	YES	91,158	5,938	46,263	8,321	30,474	-33,152
160		Imbrium	26,588	15,564	1,708	348,931	270,867	309,899	13	5	9	YES	85,796	26,841	54,173	34,433	31,717	-37,723
161		Imbrium	57,031	49,09	1,162			363,031			16	NO	157,097			22,689	32,067	-37,561
162		Imbrium	45,034	37,256	1,209			550,014			29	NO	81,878			18,966	32,579	-38,927
163		Imbrium	30,75	14,401	2,135	1204,784	995,239	1100,012	127	22	74,5	YES	27,954	9,486	45,238	14,765	32,989	-37,685
164		Imbrium	102,441	70,096	1,461			499,291			4	NO	205,173			124,823	35,928	-36,198

165		Procellarum	19,426	11,98	1,622	615,322	238,004	426,663	35	10	22,5	YES	45,530	17,581	23,800	18,963	36,029	-40,488
166		Procellarum	19,759	17,127	1,154			548,652			30	NO	36,014			18,288	36,825	-40,468
167		Imbrium	67,022	44,17	1,517			390,604			11	NO	171,586			35,509	36,266	-35,653
168		Imbrium	33,631	22,04	1,526			733,454			31	NO	45,853			23,660	39,205	-36,894
169		Imbrium	25,415	18,024	1,41			315,52			10	NO	80,550			31,552	40,504	-39,644
170		Imbrium	20,919	16,462	1,271	994,036	927,981	961,008	89	45	67	YES	21,768	11,169	20,622	14,343	40,879	-38,937
171		Procellarum	84,311	69,3	1,217	868,33	473,628	670,979	26	25	25,5	YES	125,654	33,397	18,945	26,313	35,446	-44,263
172		Procellarum	134,714	106,359	1,267	1735,272	353,197	1044,235	170	12	91	YES	129,007	10,207	29,433	11,475	36,625	-46,415
173		Procellarum	1,562	0,91	1,716			103,395			4	NO	15,107			25,849	46,467	-41,507
174		Procellarum	92,695	65,64	1,412	797,588	304,733	551,161	76	10	43	YES	168,181	10,495	30,473	12,818	48,043	-49,625
175		Procellarum	15,694	7,16	2,192	440,931	298,326	369,629	26	4	15	YES	42,459	16,959	74,582	24,642	48,033	-48,413
176	Rima Sharp	Procellarum	393,176	251,296	1,565	1688,504	389,336	1038,92	308	17	162,5	YES	378,447	5,482	22,902	6,393	48,007	-49,622
177		Procellarum	99,12	73,923	1,341	438,527	358,314	398,421	10	10	10	YES	248,782	43,853	35,831	39,842	48,465	-52,344
178		Procellarum	27,207	25,884	1,051			533,302			34	NO	51,016			15,685	48,181	-58,871
179		Procellarum	10,211	9,714	1,051			833,099			26	NO	12,257			32,042	54,856	-37,376
180		Imbrium	55,211	39,589	1,395			1965,052			100	NO	28,096			19,651	52,325	-32,128
181		Imbrium	149,967	104,975	1,429			420,286			16	NO	356,821			26,268	46,857	-26,841
182		Imbrium	72,892	63,15	1,154			914,964			21	NO	79,667			43,570	47,694	-22,679
183	Rimae Maupertuis	Imbrium	79,268	37,358	2,122			1355,644			98	NO	58,473			13,833	51,708	-23,092
184		Imbrium	56,175	21,269	2,641			931,912			61	NO	60,279			15,277	51,604	-22,331
185		Imbrium	19,431	12,469	1,558			1619,044			69	NO	12,002			23,464	52,436	-22,319
186		Imbrium	43,84	33,43	1,311	2379,071	873,549	1626,31	120	140	130	YES	26,957	19,826	6,240	12,510	51,772	-18,362
187		Imbrium	17,223	11,98	1,438	2379,071	756,836	1567,954	120	29	74,5	YES	10,984	19,826	26,098	21,046	51,772	-18,362
188		Imbrium	29,389	14,881	1,975			729,703			47	NO	40,275			15,526	51,93	-15,996
189		Imbrium	176,788	88,173	2,005	3017,967	666,055	1842,011	445	8	226,5	YES	95,976	6,782	83,257	8,132	51,571	-12,826
190	Rimae Plato	Imbrium	146,347	129,4	1,131	4006,117	3163,581	3584,849	494	207	350,5	YES	40,824	8,110	15,283	10,228	52,481	-5,468
191		Imbrium	150,958	108,137	1,396			2461,147			184	NO	61,336			13,376	51,695	-0,506
192	Rima Vladimir	Imbrium	41,748	37,716	1,107	2113,39	865,867	1489,628	414	112	263	YES	28,026	5,105	7,731	5,664	25,367	-0,934

193		Imbrium	33,845	25,265	1,34			593,388			17	NO	57,037			34,905	20,681	-3,549
194		Imbrium	15,803	9,594	1,647			278,68			16	NO	56,707			17,418	20,681	-3,549
195		Imbrium	7,989	4,219	1,894			392,548			19	NO	20,352			20,660	21,842	-3,932
196		Imbrium	139,993	108,256	1,293			431,139			14	NO	324,705			30,796	25,46	-10,023
197		Imbrium	37,206	17,634	2,11			664,206			22	NO	56,016			30,191	18,708	-7,439
198		Imbrium	133,906	72,782	1,84			501,996			13	NO	266,747			38,615	17,557	-8,492
199		Imbrium	14,916	12,716	1,173			223,77			32	NO	66,658			6,993	19,696	-7,053
200		Imbrium	52,767	39,393	1,34	711,963	747,669	729,816	33	35	34	YES	72,302	21,575	21,362	21,465	18,858	-10,889
201		Sinus Aestuum	9,328	8,959	1,041	440,179	379,514	409,847	18	17	17,5	YES	22,760	24,454	22,324	23,420	13,208	-5,232
202	Rimae Bode	Sinus Aestuum	44,679	29,322	1,524	610,098	379,141	494,62	68	8	38	YES	90,330	8,972	47,393	13,016	10,603	-3,124
203		Sinus Aestuum	3,428	2,724	1,258	450,486	277,581	364,034	39	17	28	YES	9,417	11,551	16,328	13,001	13,131	-1,831
204	Rimae Bode	Sinus Aestuum	21,235	18,08	1,175			672,52			37	NO	31,575			18,176	10,061	-6,117
205		Sinus Aestuum	24,644	22,409	1,1			581,187			36	NO	42,403			16,144	6,477	-9,046
206		Sinus Aestuum	10,899	9,259	1,177			532,898			23	NO	20,452			23,169	3,613	-6,059
207	Rimae Bode	Sinus Aestuum	100,547	56,087	1,793			816,685			51	NO	123,116			16,013	6,666	-3,035
208	Rimae Bode	Sinus Aestuum	119,46	59,631	2,003	887,982	927,501	907,742	74	52	63	YES	131,601	12,000	17,837	14,409	10,623	-4,375
209		Sinus Aestuum	18,863	17,095	1,103			616,989			45	NO	30,573			13,711	5,035	-0,767
210		Sinus Aestuum	10,467	9,369	1,117			411,953			16	NO	25,408			25,747	5,218	-0,99
211		Sinus Aestuum	9,629	8,095	1,189			613,167			47	NO	15,704			13,046	5,308	-0,886
212		Sinus Aestuum	15,203	13,995	1,086			805,435			32	NO	18,876			25,170	4,936	-0,617
213		Sinus Aestuum	18,493	13,06	1,416	809,924	430,452	620,188	80	14	47	YES	29,818	10,124	30,747	13,195	4,92	-0,581
214	Rima Milichius	Procellarum	148,119	103,754	1,428			372,002			24	NO	398,167			15,500	9,559	-33,186
215	Rima T.Mayer	Imbrium	55,991	38,893	1,44			423,577			35	NO	132,186			12,102	13,695	-31,064
216		Mare Smythii	25,267	23,913	1,057			806,521			48	NO	31,328			16,803	-1,474	84,712
217		Procellarum	244,904	130,489	1,877	1155,791	632,477	894,134	90	5	42,5	YES	273,901	12,842	126,495	21,038	24,419	-49,282
218		Procellarum	16,932	14,371	1,178	691,355	715,355	703,355	50	23	36,5	YES	24,073	13,827	31,102	19,270	24,352	-53,97
219		Procellarum	17,14	13,677	1,253	2970,657	1462,158	2216,408	534	206	370	YES	7,733	5,563	7,098	5,990	25,806	-47,595
220		Procellarum	97,682	78,593	1,243	1771,142	868,007	1319,575	249	34	141,5	YES	74,025	7,113	25,530	9,326	25,966	-46,929

221		Procellarum	34,06	26,905	1,266	1846,669	1501,849	1674,259	116	132	124	YES	20,343	15,920	11,378	13,502	26,381	-46,727
222		Procellarum	116,383	95,224	1,222	858,227	316,307	587,267	100	14	57	YES	198,177	8,582	22,593	10,303	26,849	-46,543
223		Procellarum	28,741	25,14	1,143			376,787			6	NO	76,279			62,798	28,803	-44,533
224		Procellarum	16,919	12,587	1,344	882,781	627,408	755,094	46	24	35	YES	22,406	19,191	26,142	21,574	26,849	-46,543
225		Procellarum	26,446	22,803	1,16	1236	866,655	1051,327	116	46	81	YES	25,155	10,655	18,840	12,979	27,485	-46,154
226		Procellarum	16,794	14,477	1,16	955,094	1004,506	979,8	82	37	59,5	YES	17,140	11,647	27,149	16,467	27,398	-46,361
227		Procellarum	88,806	52,905	1,679	1638,821	1751,783	1695,302	221	19	120	YES	52,384	7,415	92,199	14,128	26,63	-43,112
228		Procellarum	95,874	57,842	1,658	898,139	592,518	745,329	140	11	75,5	YES	128,633	6,415	53,865	9,872	26,306	-43,678
229		Procellarum	23,499	21,056	1,116	2200,28	1075,922	1638,101	108	20	64	YES	14,345	20,373	53,796	25,595	26,83	-43,204
230		Procellarum	38,566	34,57	1,116	1308,762	1300,564	1304,663	126	7	66,5	YES	29,560	10,387	185,795	19,619	26,688	-42,875
231		Procellarum	27,167	18,972	1,432	2403,389	912,249	1657,819	62	21	41,5	YES	16,387	38,764	43,440	39,947	27,263	-42,598
232		Procellarum	4,044	3,841	1,053	893,746	926,257	910,002	85	113	99	YES	4,444	10,515	8,197	9,192	27,08	-46,611
233		Procellarum	37,94	32,604	1,164			1076,52			27	NO	35,243			39,871	28,887	-45,766
234		Procellarum	8,09	7,793	1,038			492,957			19	NO	16,411			25,945	28,797	-46,87
235		Procellarum	48,336	39,146	1,235	1164,205	1007,413	1085,809	153	32	92,5	YES	44,516	7,609	31,482	11,738	28,184	-47,62
236		Procellarum	55,791	44,792	1,246			1254,417			123	NO	44,476			10,199	28,482	-48,156
237		Procellarum	2,867	2,584	1,11	405,578	1076,047	740,813	71	60	65,5	YES	3,870	5,712	17,934	11,310	29,632	-47,592
238		Procellarum	90,464	71,679	1,262	1453,374	1075,684	1264,529	245	20	132,5	YES	71,540	5,932	53,784	9,544	28,082	-49,709
239		Procellarum	32,142	28,25	1,138	1526,776	1089,464	1308,12	254	58	156	YES	24,571	6,011	18,784	8,385	29,398	-49,025
240		Procellarum	63,717	37,212	1,712	2364,383	599,189	1481,786	145	19	82	YES	43,000	16,306	31,536	18,071	28,354	-51,006
241		Procellarum	15,629	14,831	1,054	1098,71	472,889	785,8	235	31	133	YES	19,889	4,675	15,254	5,908	25,146	-54,194
242		Procellarum	15,267	14,777	1,033	1098,71	1450,64	1274,675	235	21	128	YES	11,977	4,675	69,078	9,958	25,14	-54,352
243		Procellarum	10,12	9,828	1,03			1415,751			149	NO	7,148			9,502	26,007	-42,603
244		Procellarum	23,389	17,133	1,365	2453,892	2893,244	2673,568	232	60	146	YES	8,748	10,577	48,221	18,312	25,839	-42,473
245		Procellarum	21,862	12,942	1,689	837,654	674,761	756,208	132	47	89,5	YES	28,910	6,346	14,357	8,449	25,871	-42,322
246		Procellarum	23,209	21,24	1,093	783,241	585,603	684,422	69	25	47	YES	33,910	11,351	23,424	14,562	27,801	-46,396
247		Procellarum	40,359	37,686	1,071			543,152			46	NO	74,305			11,808	21,219	-49,703
248		Procellarum	10,959	10,949	1,001	1372,151	808,907	1090,529	66	78	72	YES	10,049	20,790	10,371	15,146	27,674	-41,302

249		Procellarum	6,484	6,445	1,006			835,811			92	NO	7,758			9,085	27,45	-41,714
250		Procellarum	14,411	10,141	1,421			723,043			23	NO	19,931			31,437	26,851	-42,513
251		Procellarum	16,553	12,436	1,331	937,381	1122,981	1030,181	110	60	85	YES	16,068	8,522	18,716	12,120	24,405	-50,967
252		Procellarum	18,471	13,402	1,378	1464,384	772,672	1118,528	127	22	74,5	YES	16,514	11,531	35,121	15,014	24,479	-50,955
253		Eijkman	80,942	42,668	1,897			1690,207			140	NO	47,889			12,073	-63,647	-133,685
254		Procellarum	45,198	36,561	1,236			335,904			11	NO	134,556			30,537	-16,371	-23,39
255		Procellarum	5,595	3,556	1,573			410,821			23	NO	13,619			17,862	9,292	-48,505
256		Procellarum	3,551	1,345	2,64	606,874	384,358	495,616	43	18	30,5	YES	7,165	14,113	21,353	16,250	9,161	-48,607
257		Procellarum	2,733	1,928	1,418			288,83			18	NO	9,462			16,046	9,182	-48,559
258		Procellarum	219,059	154,386	1,419	413,708	290,377	352,043	16	10	13	YES	622,251	25,857	29,038	27,080	14,873	-60,399
259		Imbrium	9,807	8,371	1,172			947,303			34	NO	10,353			27,862	32,032	-37,373
260		Imbrium	6,486	5,903	1,099	779,328	338,689	559,009	28	6	17	YES	11,603	27,833	56,448	32,883	32,974	-36,319
261		Imbrium	29,003	24,367	1,19	576,272	340,719	117,777	54	9	31,5	YES	246,254	10,672	37,858	3,739	32,691	-38,033
262		Procellarum	4,929	4,675	1,054			265,461			11	NO	18,568			24,133	9,436	-33,166
263		Procellarum	7,095	6,736	1,053			445,202			20	NO	15,937			22,260	23,495	-52,644
264		Procellarum	6,962	6,835	1,019	857,933	664,21	761,072	133	30	81,5	YES	9,148	6,451	22,140	9,338	27,344	-46,586

Atlas of venusian sinuous rilles

ID	Name	Location	Confidence	Type	Lenght (km)	Distance (km)	Sinuosity (adim)	Width Source (m)	Width End (m)	Width Avarage (m)	Depth Source (m)	Depth End (m)	Depth Avarage (m)	Source?	Width/Lenght (adim)	Width/Depth Source (adim)	Width/Depth End (adim)	Width/Depth Avarage (adim)	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)
1		Podaga Tholus	YES	Sinuous Rille	131,028	82,837	1,582	2631,42	567,524	1599,472				YES	12,207				-56,656	1,521
2		Bau Corona	YES	Sinuous Rille	58,533	43,316	1,351			442,204				NO	7,555				52,577	-100,707
3		Seoritsu Farra	YES	Sinuous Rille	116,014	78,84	1,472	402,556	252,732	327,644				YES	2,824				-32,575	11,297
4		Seoritsu Farra	YES	Sinuous Rille	120,298	107,01	1,124	2907,559	2608,109	2757,834				YES	22,925				-32,654	16,897
5		Seoritsu Farra	YES	Sinuous Rille	117,436	100,949	1,163	3041,31	996,822	2019,066				YES	17,193				-32,654	16,897
6		Stuart	YES	Sinuous Rille	20,675	17,125	1,207			1086,518				NO	52,552				-31,392	17,558
7		Tapati Vallis	YES	Sinuous Rille	96,317	67,119	1,435	547,526	212,032	379,779				YES	3,943				27,611	-55,366
8		Alcott	YES	Sinuous Rille	115,201	109,619	1,051	4191,843	3658,536	3925,19				YES	34,073				-59,54	-6,932
9		Jord Corona	YES	Sinuous Rille	52,278	44,989	1,162	2818,125	900,878	1859,502				YES	35,569				-58,544	-10,016
10		Quetzalpetlati Corona	YES	Sinuous Rille	333,821	309,429	1,079			2821,533				NO	8,452				-67,865	-1,107
11		Quetzalpetlati Corona	YES	Sinuous Rille	224,174	185,59	1,208			749,33				NO	3,343				-68,109	-2,072
12		Jord Corona	YES	Sinuous Rille	41,715	38,602	1,081	998,161	568,509	783,335				YES	18,778				-58,914	-9,76
13		Jord Corona	YES	Sinuous Rille	59,069	57,442	1,028	1634,002	1327,81	1480,906				YES	25,071				-59,316	-11,207
14		Cleopatra	YES	Sinuous Rille	96,558	88,574	1,09			2195,257			40	NO	22,735			55	66,318	5,199
17		Nastya	YES	Sinuous Rille	66,542	55,547	1,198			2119,262				NO	31,848				-50,892	-85,458
18		Nastya	YES	Sinuous Rille	349,86	237,593	1,473			2458,78				NO	7,028				-47,993	-87,739
19		Nastya	YES	Sinuous Rille	176,096	122,645	1,436	3577,264	1583,975	2580,62				YES	14,655				-48,51	-87,068
22		Khafiza	YES	Sinuous Rille	28,596	24,014	1,191			1017,141				NO	35,569				5,286	-61,145
23		Khafiza	YES	Sinuous Rille	25,978	24,058	1,08			645,56				NO	24,850				5,644	-60,803
24		Khafiza	YES	Sinuous Rille	30,775	27,816	1,106			919,988				NO	29,894				5,702	-60,882
31		Rudneva	YES	Sinuous Rille	338,708	285,738	1,185			1239,724				NO	3,660				80,741	177,415
32		Rudneva	YES	Sinuous Rille	174,353	147,233	1,184			1090,107				NO	6,252				80,571	178,621
33		Rudneva	YES	Sinuous Rille	792,959	452,121	1,754			1592,296				NO	2,008				81,635	-179,994
34		Rudneva	YES	Sinuous Rille	266,056	120,952	2,2			1661,748				NO	6,246				80,46	175,223
35		Dickinson	YES	Sinuous Rille	66,364	56,26	1,18	1552,751	1436,989	1494,87				YES	22,525				74,041	177,902

36		Hapei	YES	Sinuuous Rille	28,032	19,385	1,446	992,033	824,035	908,034			YES	32,393				66,667	177,752
37		Rafiga	YES	Sinuuous Rille	65,867	60,669	1,086			513,551			NO	7,797				62,089	179,259
38		Rafiga	YES	Sinuuous Rille	24,824	13,996	1,774			396,792			NO	15,984				62,39	177,777
39		Datsolalee	NO	Sinuuous Rille	10,629	5,582	1,904			339,053		54	NO	31,899		6		38,194	179,301
40		Datsolalee	NO	Sinuuous Rille	30,075	28,562	1,053			397,179			NO	13,206				36,711	179,588
41		Athena Tessera	NO	Sinuuous Rille	10,848	7,983	1,359	628,186	345,483	486,835			YES	44,878				34,42	179,619
42		Athena Tessera	NO	Sinuuous Rille	5,205	3,335	1,561	329,181	218,504	273,843			YES	52,612				34,572	178,487
43		Athena Tessera	YES	Sinuuous Rille	11,053	9,891	1,117			322,202		101	NO	29,151		3		33,992	179,132
44		Athena Tessera	YES	Sinuuous Rille	52,213	50,382	1,036	1619,847	1223,316	1421,582		418	YES	27,227		3		31,984	177,487
45		Halle	YES	Sinuuous Rille	37,98	33,088	1,148	765,186	518,751	641,969		15	YES	16,903		43		-19,946	144,799
46		Halle	YES	Sinuuous Rille	105,845	92,791	1,141	1367,899	793,041	1080,47		25	YES	10,208		43		-19,946	144,799
47		Enyo Fossae	YES	Sinuuous Rille	67,782	53,562	1,265			5883,532			NO	86,801				-60,255	-12,325
48		Enyo Fossae	YES	Sinuuous Rille	84,016	68,897	1,219	6602,879	3441,743	5022,311			YES	59,778				-60,308	-11,972
49		Enyo Fossae	YES	Sinuuous Rille	29,541	27,074	1,091	3169,351	2483,245	2826,298			YES	95,674				-60,294	-12,366
50		Enyo Fossae	YES	Sinuuous Rille	140,293	127,028	1,104	2086,674	564,852	1325,763			YES	9,450				-60,211	-11,731
51		Enyo Fossae	YES	Sinuuous Rille	99,666	98,824	1,009	822,638	470,098	646,368			YES	6,485				-60,803	-11,052
52		Enyo Fossae	YES	Sinuuous Rille	43,528	40,72	1,069	1432,378	1718,174	1575,276			YES	36,190				-60,107	-11,072
53		Enyo Fossae	YES	Sinuuous Rille	63,481	61,265	1,036	1686,797	750,387	1218,592			YES	19,196				-60,508	-10,427
54		Jord Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	275,713	275,461	1,001	2600,961	998,642	1799,802			YES	6,528				-57,567	-12,15
55		Quetzalpetlati Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	299,316	269,626	1,11	1817,405	322,41	1069,908			YES	3,575				-68,663	-2,22
56		Quetzalpetlati Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	147,989	108,625	1,362	2172,439	474,378	1323,409			YES	8,943				-68,546	-2,928
57		Quetzalpetlati Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	64,671	27,481	2,353	1030,549	1998,035	1514,292			YES	23,415				-68,776	-2,352
58		Quetzalpetlati Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	294,06	270,32	1,088	4600,133	751,067	2675,6			YES	9,099				-68,807	-0,156
59		Quetzalpetlati Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	207,666	196,737	1,056	2240,117	710,596	1475,357			YES	7,104				-68,406	0,213
60		Boala Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	285,329	283,785	1,005	2313,582	528,21	1420,896			YES	4,980				-69,426	2,548
61		Boala Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	113,965	92,678	1,23			2024,232			NO	17,762				-70,413	0,102
62		Boala Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	129,851	99,998	1,299	1901,873	405,093	1153,483			YES	8,883				-69,595	3,648
63		Boala Corona	YES	Sinuuous Rille	63,001	56,032	1,124			2041,417			NO	32,403				-69,687	4,776

205		Estelle	YES	Sinuou Rille	14,26	12,433	1,147	753,508	239,568	496,538	38	10	24	YES	34,820	20	24	21	0,477	91,106
206		Doris	YES	Sinuou Rille	7,319	6,322	1,158			476,483			52	NO	65,102			9	2,858	88,041
207		Doris	NO	Sinuou Rille	17,115	13,123	1,304			967,149			14	NO	56,509			69	3,743	90,066
208		Doris	NO	Sinuou Rille	10,662	9,206	1,158			486,446			15	NO	45,624			32	3,598	90,86
209		Susanna	YES	Sinuou Rille	104,312	83,173	1,254			485,288			13	NO	4,652			37	4,887	91,51
210		Susanna	YES	Sinuou Rille	15,141	14,004	1,081			272,286			6	NO	17,983			45	5,003	90,916
211		Susanna	YES	Sinuou Rille	36,315	33,824	1,074	559,267	262,109	410,688	71	14	42	YES	11,309	8	19	10	5,346	91,441
212		Susanna	YES	Sinuou Rille	25,428	20,505	1,24			431,192			15	NO	16,957			29	5,458	91,103
213		Susanna	NO	Sinuou Rille	9,646	6,113	1,578	453,5	279,063	366,282	65	24	44	YES	37,972	7	12	8	5,484	91,159
214		Susanna	YES	Sinuou Rille	43,429	39,703	1,094	347,968	295,883	321,926	17	6	12	YES	7,413	20	49	27	5,612	91,34
215		Susanna	YES	Sinuou Rille	37,095	29,407	1,261			476,34			5	NO	12,841			95	5,798	90,69
216		Atse Etsan Corona	YES	Sinuou Rille	4,825	4,41	1,094	460,084	218,781	339,433	36	20	28	YES	70,349	13	11	12	9,02	92,495
217		Atse Etsan Corona	YES	Sinuou Rille	87,574	77,14	1,135	329,08	268,734	298,907			22	YES	3,413			14	9,362	90,851
218		Atse Etsan Corona	NO	Sinuou Rille	7,117	6,717	1,06			457,512			12	NO	64,284			38	9,561	91,086
219		Atse Etsan Corona	YES	Sinuou Rille	7,278	6,537	1,113	411,013	237,882	324,448	23	16	20	YES	44,579	18	15	16	9,721	90,488
220		Amaya	YES	Sinuou Rille	3,946	3,436	1,148	327,688	271,862	299,775	4	4	4	YES	75,969	82	68	75	10,756	91,107
221		Ezili Tholus	YES	Sinuou Rille	81,193	60,789	1,336	614,598	306,825	460,712	46	18	32	YES	5,674	13	17	14	24,067	91,611
222		Eurynome Corona	YES	Sinuou Rille	21,695	16,957	1,279	342,067	218,983	280,525	8	3	6	YES	12,930	43	73	47	29,163	97,153
223		Eurynome Corona	YES	Sinuou Rille	23,276	19,967	1,166	507,461	331,409	419,435	44	4	24	YES	18,020	12	83	17	28,958	97,119
224		Eurynome Corona	YES	Sinuou Rille	34,756	25,639	1,356			571,821			7	NO	16,452			82	27,832	94,783
225		Eurynome Corona	YES	Sinuou Rille	30,967	25,966	1,193	403,707	268,172	335,94	57	8	32	YES	10,848	7	34	10	27,184	95,064
226		Shimti Tessera	YES	Sinuou Rille	45,333	28,006	1,619	393,149	165,226	279,188	6	3	4	YES	6,159	66	55	70	29,206	95,802
227		Shimti Tessera	YES	Sinuou Rille	20,726	15,312	1,354	311,693	237,673	274,683				YES	13,253				29,346	96,036
228		Datsolalee	NO	Sinuou Rille	7,071	6,449	1,096			241,36				NO	34,134				39,55	178,404
229		Datsolalee	NO	Sinuou Rille	9,596	8,465	1,134	615,382	182,817	399,1				YES	41,590				38,463	178,594
230		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuou Rille	110,494	79,165	1,396	669,248	149,635	409,442				YES	3,706				-2,242	-86,497
231		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuou Rille	21,664	14,805	1,463	354,374	200,662	277,518				YES	12,810				-2,185	-86,422
232		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuou Rille	7,296	5,103	1,43	210,925	114,063	162,494				YES	22,272				-2,231	-86,457

233		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuus Rille	10,344	5,178	1,998	176,1	201,617	188,859			YES	18,258					-1,687	-86,973
234		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuus Rille	171,659	98,242	1,747	399,987	208,489	304,238			YES	1,772					-1,735	-87,022
235		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuus Rille	10,738	8,946	1,2	615,163	427,589	521,376			YES	48,554					-2,294	-86,644
236		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuus Rille	15,113	14,214	1,063	302,2	225,364	263,782			YES	17,454					-1,569	-87,379
237		Phoebe Regio	YES	Sinuus Rille	33,24	31,418	1,058	378,936	356,021	367,479			YES	11,055					-2,701	-85,596
238	Samundra Vallis	Carson	YES	Sinuus Rille	184,483	139,575	1,322	6320,757	2220,493	4270,625			YES	23,149					-23,785	-12,996
241	Belisama Vallis	Ishtar Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	403,846	319,333	1,265	4901,49	1936,322	3418,906	175	30	102	YES	8,466	28	65	34	50,629	21,295
242		Dunne-Musun Corona	YES	Sinuus Rille	250,574	242,321	1,034	2290,888	599,007	1444,948			YES	5,767					-59,549	83,449
243		Dunne-Musun Corona	YES	Sinuus Rille	24,867	22,865	1,088	479,239	389,071	434,155			YES	17,459					-59,319	83,42
244		Dunne-Musun Corona	YES	Sinuus Rille	405,668	171,203	2,37	7482,151	796,586	4139,368			YES	10,204					-59,6	86,196
247		Lada Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	77,665	68,975	1,126			871,725			NO	11,224					-60,514	159,892
249		Lada Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	83,007	69,449	1,195	5047,126	3692,758	4369,942			YES	52,645					-60,772	160,761
250		Lada Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	49,614	48,066	1,032	551,06	356,623	453,842			YES	9,147					-60,241	170,3
258	Umaga Vallis	Mahuea Tholus	YES	Sinuus Rille	667,103	434,822	1,534			1562,096			NO	2,342					-50,521	149,771
259	Helmut Vallis	Mahuea Tholus	YES	Sinuus Rille	332,841	279,357	1,191			1127,908		4	NO	3,389			282		-34,028	171,111
261	Vishera Vallis	Aphrodite Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	806,969	579,443	1,393			1481,496		27	NO	1,836			55		-32,806	161,993
263		Aphrodite Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	145,374	55,947	2,598			1031,896			NO	7,098					-34,516	155,194
268		Payne Gaposchkin Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	87,202	80,763	1,08	1125,336	379,282	752,309			YES	8,627					-24,827	-164,904
269		Payne Gaposchkin Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	35,493	28,247	1,257	2799,506	276,47	1537,988			YES	43,332					-24,827	-164,904
270		Ulpu	YES	Sinuus Rille	476,5	440,389	1,082			1220,374		9	NO	2,561			136		-32,365	176,793
271		Ulpu	YES	Sinuus Rille	117,806	109,824	1,073	2795,637	1063,032	1929,335			YES	16,377					-35,098	-179,877
272		Aphrodite Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	91,204	81,075	1,125			446,688		37	NO	4,898			12		-15,931	177,28
273		Aphrodite Terra	YES	Sinuus Rille	50,763	47,06	1,079			567,638		22	NO	11,182			26		-17,544	175,47
274		Langtry	YES	Sinuus Rille	16,599	13,771	1,205	710,838	442,415	576,627	51	4	28	YES	34,739	14	111	21	-18,02	153,917
275	Ahsabkab	Ix Chel Chasma	YES	Sinuus Rille	187,353	118,496	1,581			1088,858		17	NO	5,812			64		-25,151	79,364
276	Alajen Vallis	Carson	YES	Sinuus Rille	276,031	215,575	1,28			1088,975			NO	3,945					-3,81	-24,408
277	Albys Vallis	Agnesi	YES	Sinuus Rille	361,423	139,712	2,587	3281,81	2504,852	2893,331			YES	8,005					-39,09	29,195

355		Higgins	YES	Sinuus Rille	33,809	31,788	1,064	408,287	209,056	308,672				YES	9,130					5,999	-119,019
356		Higgins	YES	Sinuus Rille	62,751	56,539	1,11	346,558	268,511	307,535				YES	4,901					3,025	-119,801
357		Higgins	YES	Sinuus Rille	30,324	26,068	1,163	337,775	192,716	265,246				YES	8,747					2,943	-119,868
358		Higgins	YES	Sinuus Rille	25,198	21,761	1,158	889,938	439,912	664,925				YES	26,388					2,33	-119,248
359		Higgins	YES	Sinuus Rille	20,685	17,76	1,165	256,02	260,838	258,429				YES	12,494					2,233	-119,14
360		Higgins	YES	Sinuus Rille	36,342	29,567	1,229	617,385	545,948	581,667				YES	16,005					-0,188	-117,808
361		Javine Corona	YES	Sinuus Rille	13,538	12,374	1,094			332,95				NO	24,594					-6,639	-107,568
362		Javine Corona	YES	Sinuus Rille	18,863	18,656	1,011	509,087	337,693	423,39				YES	22,446					-6,808	-108,225
363		Castro	YES	Sinuus Rille	41,967	30,389	1,381	687,712	469,098	578,405				YES	13,782					2,315	-121,04
364		Toklas	YES	Sinuus Rille	55,603	50,432	1,103	1073,119	183,259	628,189				YES	11,298					2,463	-85,687
365		Toklas	YES	Sinuus Rille	8,644	8,405	1,028	236,936	224,039	230,488				YES	26,665					3,786	-85,356
366		Toklas	YES	Sinuus Rille	18,893	14,867	1,271	240,269	194,123	217,196				YES	11,496					3,136	-86,597
367		Domnika	YES	Sinuus Rille	64,437	43,777	1,472	950,875	403,957	677,416				YES	10,513					16,51	-67,533
368		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	67,554	61,167	1,104	4593,68	1597,433	3095,557				YES	45,823					16,102	-61,208
369		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	6,596	6,187	1,066	1034,186	498,847	766,517				YES	116,209					15,954	-61,702
370		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	40,073	27,347	1,465	634,389	1252,906	943,648				YES	23,548					15,872	-61,576
371		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	155,702	136,598	1,14	711,563	334,487	523,025				YES	3,359					15,608	-61,436
372		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	74,872	68,969	1,086	309,474	449,202	379,338				YES	5,066					15,754	-61,683
373		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	121,814	77,41	1,574	713,298	350,188	531,743				YES	4,365					17,426	-61,46
374		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	24,768	22,436	1,104	648,093	407,219	527,656				YES	21,304					16,981	-59,799
375		Grizodubova Patera	YES	Sinuus Rille	67,524	54,786	1,233	545,545	485,245	515,395				YES	7,633					16,198	-62,083
376	Olokun Vallis	Snegurochka Planitia	YES	Sinuus Rille	802,574	795,771	1,009			2373,581				NO	2,957					81,706	-89,422
379	Lunang Vallis	Lakshmi Planum	YES	Sinuus Rille	548,506	520,536	1,054	1928,424	535,054	1231,739				YES	2,246					67,97	-49,132
380		Lakshmi Planum	YES	Sinuus Rille	77,714	59,271	1,311			903,014				NO	11,620					69,036	-58,689
381		Djata Fluctus	YES	Sinuus Rille	13,062	8,597	1,519			355,802				NO	27,239					66,829	-54,579
382		Colette Paters	YES	Sinuus Rille	72,338	51,293	1,41	3544,586	290,41	1917,498				YES	26,507					66,291	-42,747
385		Podaga Tholus	YES	Sinuus Rille	41,56	34,917	1,19	848,582	282,756	565,669				YES	13,611					-56,549	1,541
386		Podaga Tholus	YES	Sinuus Rille	19,466	19,024	1,023	400,237	212	306,119				YES	15,726					-55,935	1,778

415		Pamela	YES	Sinuuous Rille	8,825	7,995	1,104	542,289	454,708	498,499				YES	56,487				9,466	-121,774
416		Pamela	YES	Sinuuous Rille	9,499	7,975	1,191			368,749				NO	38,820				9,505	-121,648
417		Pamela	YES	Sinuuous Rille	16,151	14,058	1,149			281,849				NO	17,451				9,39	-121,839
418		Akeley	YES	Sinuuous Rille	31,847	26,874	1,185	1216,617	216,257	716,437				YES	22,496				7,867	-114,925
419		Akeley	YES	Sinuuous Rille	22,628	16,388	1,381	297,249	286,262	291,756				YES	12,894				7,858	-115,163
420		Akeley	YES	Sinuuous Rille	7,959	6,257	1,272	348,136	229,073	288,605				YES	36,261				7,738	-115,235
421		Akeley	YES	Sinuuous Rille	10,423	5,575	1,87	303,477	192,47	247,974				YES	23,791				7,613	-114,958
422		Akeley	YES	Sinuuous Rille	6,08	4,981	1,221	454,638	196,22	325,429				YES	53,525				7,836	-114,727
423		Sobra Fluctus	YES	Sinuuous Rille	9,783	8,795	1,112	667,378	319,036	493,207				YES	50,415				6,174	-114,477
424		Thaukhd Linea	YES	Sinuuous Rille	65,758	57,232	1,149	1368,129	510,25	939,19				YES	14,283				-29,272	-123,285
425		Wawalag planitia	YES	Sinuuous Rille	38,139	35,199	1,084	825,758	270,366	548,062				YES	14,370				-25,969	-140,062
426		Fedchenko Patera	YES	Sinuuous Rille	142,133	123,132	1,154	1155,797	214,009	684,903				YES	4,819				-23,555	-133,109

List of venusian canali

ID	Name	Location	Confidence	Type	Lenght (km)	Distance (km)	Sinuosity (adim)	Width Source (m)	Width End (m)	Width Avarage (m)	Depth Source (m)	Depth End (m)	Depth Avarage (m)	Source?	Width/Lenght (adim)	Width/Depth Source (adim)	Width/Depth End (adim)	Width/Depth Avarage (adim)	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)
15	Baltis Vallis	Ganiki Planitia	YES	Vallis	7052,412	4482,389	1,573			2268,291			88	NO	0,322			26	52,519	177,406
16	Sinann Vallis	Sinann Vallis	YES	Vallis	895,162	697,79	1,283			1180,378				NO	1,319				-48,293	-88,079
20		Nastya	YES	Vallis	389,08	298,973	1,301			1206,046				NO	3,100				-49,764	-85,879
21	Bennu Vallis	Sif Mons	YES	Vallis	760,144	627,415	1,212	1882,758	949,555	1416,157				YES	1,863				3,014	-17,374
25	Hoku-ao Vallis	Ganiki Planitia	YES	Vallis	525,402	480,749	1,093			1568,014			97	NO	2,984			16	29,868	164,67
26	Jutrenka Vallis	Ganiki Planitia	YES	Vallis	500,801	386,769	1,295	1382,95	898,116	1140,533	48	19	34	YES	2,277	29	47	34	29,482	154,683
27	Citlapul Vallis	Kahlo	YES	Vallis	1664,322	1472,368	1,13			2106,839				NO	1,266				-59,265	166,507
28	Vesper Vallis	Kahlo	YES	Vallis	407,848	386,354	1,056			1275,689				NO	3,128				-59,121	-179,998
29	Vesper Vallis	Kahlo	YES	Vallis	477,268	451,847	1,056			1463,773				NO	3,067				-58,694	175,743
30	Citlapul Vallis	Virginia	YES	Vallis	1993,133	1748,737	1,14			1530,022				NO	0,768				-55,758	-179,999
173	Banumbirr Vallis	Banumbirr Vallis	YES	Vallis	575,503	463,93	1,24	2317,41	2095,347	2206,379	90	119	104	YES	3,834	26	18	21	-8,627	5,128
239	Sati Vallis	Sif Mons	YES	Vallis	524,194	388,073	1,351			1285,615				NO	2,453				3,922	-25,982
240		Sif Mons	YES	Vallis	57,483	54,37	1,057			1493,126				NO	25,975				3,262	-23,46
245	Kumsong Vallis	Henie	YES	Vallis	793,942	693,818	1,144			1662,555				NO	2,094				-56,962	148,658
246	Kumsong Vallis	Henie	YES	Vallis	79,842	70,453	1,133			2154,09				NO	26,979				-59,194	152,879
248		Lada Terra	YES	Vallis	108,268	88,551	1,223	5047,126	3825,772	4436,449				YES	40,977				-60,441	161,027
251	Nahid Valles	Henie	YES	Vallis	305,177	249,417	1,224			3510,765				NO	11,504				-56,638	171,048
252	Nahid Valles	Henie	YES	Vallis	96,593	90,082	1,072			5510,228				NO	57,046				-56,165	169,555
253	Nahid Valles	Henie	YES	Vallis	599,975	448,57	1,338			2485,086				NO	4,142				-55,834	174,035
254	Khalansay Vallis	Henie	YES	Vallis	306,064	271,52	1,127			3164,203				NO	10,338				-49,14	169,135
255	Austrina Vallis	Mahuea Tholus	YES	Vallis	12,107	12,076	1,003	517,963	1009,693	763,828				YES	63,090				-49,279	-179,885
256	Austrina Vallis	Mahuea Tholus	YES	Vallis	621,66	585,355	1,062	517,963	1009,693	763,828				YES	1,229				-48,807	174,478
257	Lusaber Vallis	Mahuea Tholus	YES	Vallis	1219,758	990,475	1,231			1124,338				NO	0,922				-47,196	168,349
260	Matlalcae Vallis	Mahuea Tholus	YES	Vallis	723,946	599,015	1,209			1483,486			13	NO	2,049			114	-32,397	168,957
262	Vishera Vallis	Aphrodite Terra	YES	Vallis	761,905	524,079	1,454	1483,014	587,898	1035,456			21	YES	1,359			49	-30,701	162,886

384		Sedna Plantia	YES	Vallis	228,702	196,199	1,166			1293,764				NO	5,657				46,071	-20,3
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